

Embracing Active Travel for Health

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The SWITCH Campaign Guide and Toolbox

Practical advice for campaigns to promote a switch
from car-based travel to active modes of travel

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¹ The SWITCH project website will run at least until May 2018. Key SWITCH documentation and material will be permanently available on the Polis network website www.polisnetwork.eu

List of Acronyms

GHG	Green-house gases
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
NCD	Non-communicable diseases
PTP	Personalised Travel Planning
WHO	World Health Organisation

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1 The SWITCH project and its Campaign Guide

This Campaign Guide is perfect for you if you intend to organise or if you are involved in a campaign that aims to make people switch short car trips to more active modes of travel. It explains the general principles behind such a campaign, gives step-by-step advice on how to prepare, execute and evaluate it and provides all kinds of ready-made material and templates to make your life easier by not having to reinvent the wheel. In Chapter 7 you can find a systematic overview of all available support documents (referred to as the SWITCH Toolbox).

The Campaign Guide and the Toolbox are key outputs of the EU funded project with the programmatic title SWITCH. It supports cities, who aim to help people to “switch” from their car to active modes of travel on short urban distances through effective and professional campaigns. There are some basic principles behind every successful SWITCH campaign, which we put together in this Campaign Guide document and thus hope that this Campaign Guide will be of help to you, regardless of whether you are an experienced campaigner or whether you are trying this for the first time, whether your city is large or small, etc.

Some bits of advice are, of course, specific to certain local conditions, national frameworks etc. Therefore, we provide a “**transferability analysis**” in the SWITCH toolbox in order to sharpen your awareness for what might and what might not be transferable.

Throughout this document you will find some icons², which indicate the following:

Further background information

Checklist

Template to be edited for your own purpose

Suggested text for media

Suggested video

Furthermore you will find some **words** or **text passages in dark blue**. In the digital version of this document you can click on them to reach the corresponding resource on the SWITCH online toolbox. Readers of the paper version will find the internet addresses on page 90/91.

The essence of this Campaign Guide is also available in an online³ format at www.mobility-academy.eu/SWITCH. There you can go on a self-guided tour through the main points of a SWITCH campaign. In addition, you will find a series of inspirational questions that guide your thinking towards an implementation scenario for your own campaign. If you respond to these short questions one-by-one you can compile them all into one document at the end, which will form an excellent basis for your own written SWITCH strategy.

The Contact Phase

In this chapter you will learn how to get in touch with your potential participants and how to get them involved in your campaign.

www.switchtravel.eu

Supported by the European Union
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Screenshot from SWITCH online course

² These icons were designed by Freepik and are distributed under a free creative commons license with attribution. See www.flaticon.com/packs/enterprise

³ The SWITCH project website itself will run at least until May 2018. Key SWITCH documentation and material will be permanently available on the Polis network website www.polisnetwork.eu

Why SWITCH?

The combined distance of urban trips travelled per year by the average person has grown steadily – but we are actually moving (our bodies) less. Every day, millions of trips are made by car or other motorised private vehicles and public transport and only a small percentage by active transport modes, such as walking and cycling. Many people even talk about our sedentary lifestyles as an epidemic because the resulting negative impacts on our health and quality of life has reached unprecedented levels.

A sedentary lifestyle is a primary risk factor of non-communicable diseases (NCD) in Western Countries. According to a survey⁴ conducted in 2013 in the 28 Member State of the EU, 44% of Europeans did not meet the 150 minutes of moderate physical activity per week recommended by the World Health Organisation (WHO). Moreover, one in eight European citizens (13%) say they did not walk for ten minutes at a time on any day during the previous week. This lack of physical activity can cause major health problems for individuals and great economic costs for society as a whole⁵.

These negative trends can be reversed: A new urban mobility culture is blooming. Most cities aspire to create more people-friendly places to encourage walking and cycling by establishing new services to cater for pedestrians (i.e. wayfinding, real time multimodal information, shared and multi-modal mobility solutions) and by designing suitable infrastructure to make walking and cycling safer and more comfortable. Moving around by foot and on a bicycle is becoming easier, safer and more enjoyable. Besides that, increasing the share of walking and cycling and reducing car traffic leads to a higher quality of life in cities and is an important contribution to reduce GHG-emissions and primary energy consumption.

The EU funded SWITCH project wants to contribute to this positive change by helping planning and transport practitioners to conduct professionally organised campaigns with the aim to get people to “switch” short urban car journeys to walking and cycling. These “active modes” are not only inherently good and people’s health; in most cases, synergies with public transport, therefore mostly supportive of such people to “switch” short urban car journeys to walking and cycling. These “active modes” are not only inherently good and people’s health; in most cases, synergies with public transport, therefore mostly supportive of such campaigns.

⁴ Special Eurobarometer 412 “Sport and physical activity”. European Commission, 2013.

http://ec.europa.eu/public_opinion/archives/ebs/ebs_412_en.pdf

⁵ Global health risks. Geneva, World Health Organisation, 2009.

www.who.int/healthinfo/global_burden_disease/GlobalHealthRisks_report_full.pdf

What is a SWITCH campaign?

A SWITCH campaign uses the latest behaviour change methods to facilitate widespread shifts from car to active modes of travel; especially for short trips. Therefore, it addresses primarily car users. The key lies in the effective combination of tried and tested behaviour change approaches and their application to specific target groups on a large scale. The core of the actions are the following four elements:

- ✓ Personalised Travel Planning (PTP);
- ✓ arguments from public health;
- ✓ and ICT applications (Information and Communication Technologies);
- ✓ employed with people in a period of life change, such as moving house or starting a new job.

These four elements are fixed in every SWITCH campaign and are explained in detail in Chapter 2. Their concrete specification, however, is flexible. For example, different ICT tools can be used or different target groups can be addressed. In fact, your own SWITCH campaign has to be tailored to your specific local context with a unique combination of elements and tools.

Another defining feature of every SWITCH campaign are seven distinct phases, which are the focus of Chapter 4:

1. Recruitment phase
2. Contact phase
3. Assessing your participants' situation (baseline survey)
4. Segmentation phase
5. Motivation phase
6. Advice phase
7. Evaluation phase (explained in Chapter 5)

Target audience and Purpose of the SWITCH Campaign Guide

The primary target audience of the SWITCH Campaign Guide are practitioners in the fields of urban and transport planning as well as public health, working at local authorities, who have to and/or would like to implement a campaign that promotes a switch from car-based to active modes of travel. Local stakeholders, citizens and advocacy groups, organisations such as a chamber of commerce, etc. will also find this collection of hands-on advice useful.

Whereas some cities are already experienced in behaviour change campaigns, others are considering such an approach for the first time. The SWITCH Campaign Guide aims to be a useful companion for this broad variety of cities and local activists. In all cases, it wants to first trigger interest and motivation to prepare, implement and evaluate a SWITCH campaign. It also provides some background information about the essential components of a SWITCH campaign and – most importantly – detailed and practical guidance for implementation.

The SWITCH Campaign Guide and Toolbox consists of conceptual information and general guidance as well as a collection of ideas and ready-to-use templates for all phases of a SWITCH campaign: from the design stage via the recruitment phase and the personalised travel planning advice all the way to the evaluation of a campaign.

For more information about the SWITCH approach and the SWITCH project, please watch [the interview](#) with Regine Gericke, the initial project coordinator of the SWITCH project.

Structure of the SWITCH Campaign Guide

The following Chapters give an overview of the main characteristics of a SWITCH campaign and offer step-by-step guidance to design, prepare, implement and evaluate a SWITCH campaign. The SWITCH Campaign Guide is structured as follows:

- Chapter 2** provides an overview over the **four main elements** of a SWITCH campaign: personalised travel planning; health arguments; ICT tools; life change moments;
- Chapter 3** explains the concrete steps to **design** and **prepare** a SWITCH campaign;
- Chapter 4** describes the five phases to **implement** a SWITCH campaign;
- Chapter 5** explains how to **evaluate** a SWITCH campaign;
- Chapter 6** describes **the actual campaigns** of the five SWITCH Implementation Cities (Antwerp, Gdansk, London Borough of Hounslow, San Sebastián and Vienna).
- Toolbox** This is a collection of templates and ready-made materials that can be used and adapted for your local SWITCH campaign. Most of the material in the toolbox is available online as digital files for convenient download. Some key documents, however, are included at the end of this document.

Please note: The SWITCH Toolbox is a collection of material, which can be used and adapted for your own location situation. In concrete terms, these are digital files, which are hosted on the SWITCH website www.switchtravel.eu Most of them have been created by SWITCH's original Implementation Cities (Antwerp, Vienna, San Sebastián, Gdansk and the London Borough of Hounslow). This collection can grow even further with more material from these and other cities. In fact, you are invited to contact the SWITCH team if you would like to share some of your own material.

2 The four main elements of a SWITCH campaign

As mentioned, every SWITCH campaign consists of the following four essential components:

- ✓ Personalised Travel Planning (PTP);
- ✓ arguments from **public health**;
- ✓ and **ICT applications** (Information and Communication Technologies);
- ✓ employed with people in a **period of life change**, such as moving house or starting a new job.

These elements form the most important building blocks of a successful campaign, while leaving room for adaptation and adjustment for a tailored design which fits perfectly to your city's local conditions.

In other words, it's not a matter of **copying** what other cities have done before but of **understanding** the underlying principles that will allow you to develop an effective campaign for your city. This chapter provides these basic considerations and is complemented by examples in the Toolbox.

Personalised Travel Planning

Personalised Travel Planning (PTP) is a form of individual communication (also called "dialogue marketing"), which relies on close personal and tailor-made contact with targeted individuals in order to make it easier for them to change their travel behaviour. Werner Brög from the company Socialdata was seminal in developing this concept⁶. It is characterised by a set of clearly defined steps and ensures that a campaign follows a clear and comprehensive sequence of activities.

PTP typically sensitises people about their often unquestioned mobility routines. As a first step, participants are invited to rethink their everyday travel behaviour and identify realistic alternatives to car trips in the form of active modes, walking and cycling and public transport options. In short, PTP aims to:

- ✓ identify and fill individual knowledge gaps;
- ✓ raise awareness about the negative individual and societal consequences of car dependent lifestyles;
- ✓ inform about the economic and health benefits of active travel;
- ✓ show individually suitable alternatives;
- ✓ motivate and reward changes in travel habits.

PTP addresses both information deficits and subjective barriers that people have about how they travel.

There is an overwhelming amount of travel-related information available from various sources. However, this information needs to be actively accessed by people and interpreted to suit their specific situation. This individual interpretation requires effort and typically certain skills (e.g. knowing how to read a timetable). Not everyone is able or motivated to do this.

In addition, information – even if customised – does not typically trigger long-lasting changes in people's travel routines. People have subjective barriers like the fear of doing something wrong, getting lost, a lack of reminders (at least initially), the feeling of being "the only one", etc.

PTP can help by setting impulses to break with routines and to lower psychological barriers. By focusing on individuals directly and showing them how they can personally benefit from custom-made alternatives, PTP reminds and rewards them by giving them a feeling that they are part of a wider SWITCH community.

Health arguments

Public and personal health arguments can be very effective in promoting active travel because the knowledge about the very real social and individual health benefits of walking and cycling can be a strong motivator for behaviour change. They can be used to both garner support from local stakeholders (e.g. chamber of commerce) and to trigger a reflection process among individual travellers.

Local stakeholders are most likely to be interested in scientific and statistical data (please be careful about the credibility of your sources), which includes facts about:

- ✓ societal effects of physical inactivity and sedentary behaviour;
- ✓ prevalence of chronic diseases (obesity, diabetes, cardiovascular diseases, back problems, etc.);
- ✓ health benefits of regular physical activity / active lifestyles;
- ✓ impacts of car-based travel on workers' productivity, health and absent days.

For more details see the presentation of Janet Djomba – a member of the SWITCH team – on these issues, given in a **recorded webinar**⁷ or in a **short interview**.

⁶ See for example: Brög, W. et al. (2009) Evaluation of voluntary travel behaviour change Experiences from three continents. Transport Policy, Vol. 16, No. 6, pp. 281–292 www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0967070X09001036

⁷ See www.youtube.com/watch?v=of3iyXqLmQM

While these scientific arguments might be of great interest to local stakeholders and politicians, the members of your **target group** (i.e. the participants of your campaign) are probably more curious about very practical and ideally individualised information concerning the **health benefits** of active travel and how to achieve them, such as:

- ✓ someone's individual "distance" from established recommendations about physical activity⁸;
- ✓ potential improvements to someone's personal health condition;
- ✓ how to meet **medical recommendations** by using active travel;
- ✓ how to include physical activity in daily routines.

Regardless of the target group, health facts should be presented in an attractive and easy to understand way for that group. Ideally, your health information messages and how they are presented are also specific to your particular target group. For example, older people might respond more positively to different information than children or workers or immigrants etc.

The Toolbox contains a valuable collection of health related information, including one-page **factsheets** for walking, cycling and the use of health arguments that you can use for your specific local needs.

Use of ICT tools

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) tools can be particularly valuable for a SWITCH campaign for a number of reasons:

- ✓ to collect data on travel behaviour and activity levels and
- ✓ to motivate and support behavioural change.

If you use them to collect data about your target population's travel routines, they can help you to objectively assess the effectiveness of your campaign and to understand the reasons for it. Data gathered through ICT tools can also help you to formulate specific questions for the evaluation surveys and for the qualitative evaluation (see below). For example, you might detect surprising patterns in people's travel routines. In that case, you can address these points in your follow-up interviews.

ICT tools can and should also be used for motivation and to support behavioural changes by providing practical information such as maps, way finding, the location of rental bicycles or noise-reduced walking routes.

ICT tools also have the capability of reminding and motivating people. For example, they can allow their smartphones to track their movement and to obtain automatically generated feedback about their travel behaviour and their physical activity level – and related health impacts. If desired, they can share this data with friends, family members and co-workers and thus enter a voluntary, friendly competition, which has been shown to be particularly effective. These and other tools can also be used to incentivise and reward participants, either directly as part of the SWITCH campaign or indirectly as part of a competition between groups of people (e.g. between schools or workplaces).

ICT tools come in a variety of forms and approaches. The four most commonly used types of tools are:

1. Devices to automatically monitor one's own behaviour and health impact (e.g. **heart rate monitor**, **step counters**, **GPS watches**).
2. Websites where participants can obtain information and log their travel data (this requires a higher level of commitment from the user).
3. Apps for Smartphones, both mainstream products from play- or app-stores (low cost and widely available) and custom software (higher set-up costs).
4. Devices (and usage protocols, games etc.) provided by third parties such as **"Beat the Street"** in the UK.

⁸ For example: World Health Organisation (2010) Global recommendations on physical activity for health. Available at http://whqlibdoc.who.int/publications/2010/9789241599979_eng.pdf?ua=1 on 21 May 2015. (Archived by WebCite® at <http://www.webcitation.org/6Yh1QRG37>)

Good Practice

The **"Wien zu Fuß"** App (www.wienzufuss.at/app), for example, has a built-in step counter, a route planner and features a "treasure hunt" for 1000 virtual diamonds that are hidden throughout the city. The latter point is an example of the "gamification" approach that can be part of a SWITCH campaign.

Some concrete examples of potentially useful ICT tools are given in Chapter 3 – "Think about suitable ICT tools". It is important to note that the use of ICT tools has implications in terms of **data protection and privacy issues**. Make sure that you use them with utmost sensitivity and you build in safeguarding mechanisms to ensure no data leaks to unauthorised parties. Be also aware that the use of some ICT-services may unintentionally exclude certain groups of people.

For a good overview about the use of ICT tools, see the **presentation** of Regine Gericke, the initial project leader of the SWITCH team.

Life change moments

People's mobility patterns are rarely based on cognitive decisions. Instead, we typically travel in "auto-pilot mode" through our cities and don't question why we travel the way we travel. In other words, we are guided by extremely powerful habits.

However, at certain points in our lives we are forced to rethink our routines. This is when the old ones have lost their usefulness. For example, because your car has broken down, you've started a job in a new location, you have moved house, you are going to a different school, to name just a few examples. In such situations, you have to reinvent the way you meet your mobility needs.

These "life change moments" inject a moment of reflection into our lives and they offer unique opportunities to create new, healthier and more sustainable routines. A SWITCH campaign is designed to grasp precisely these opportunities. The Good Practice box describes the life change moments upon which the five SWITCH

Implementation Cities focus. But there can be many others, for example:

- ✓ People who recently moved from one school (type) to another;
- ✓ People who had a recent change to their household (children born, elderly parents moved in, young adults moved out);
- ✓ People who recently got rid of their car;
- ✓ People who recently bought a pedelec or an e-Bike;
- ✓ People whose children started to travel autonomously.

Ideally, the participants for your campaign are recruited directly when the life change event takes place, for example when they get medical advice for more physical activity; when they sign a rental contract but have not moved yet, or right after they have moved; the moment a road section is closed down for construction; they are starting at a new school or work place.

Be aware that the point in time when you contact these people will influence the strategy of your campaign evaluation (see Chapter 3 – "Decide on the best timing of your campaign").

Good Practice

The five SWITCH Implementation Cities worked with the following target groups:

- ✓ People who recently received medical advice for more physically activity;
- ✓ People who recently moved;
- ✓ People affected by major (infrastructural) changes such as a long-term road closure;
- ✓ People who recently started a new job;
- ✓ Children who recently started school.

3 Designing and preparing your SWITCH campaign

Before you even tell the public about your SWITCH campaign, a lot has to be prepared in the background. The better designed and prepared the campaign is, the more successful it will be. This will become clear in light of the general sequence of a SWITCH campaign, which always consists of several distinct steps:

1. You need to get in contact with your target persons. Therefore, you will need contact data and communication channels to get in touch with them.
2. Once you are in contact with persons of your target group, you need to motivate them by offering information and incentives to become participants of your campaign.
3. Once you have them on board, you provide them with customized information and incentives. You also offer them personalized advice and material that helps participants to change behaviour.
4. To maintain the behavioural change you get in contact with them after the information again.

It might make sense to glance at this Chapter 3 very briefly at first and to come back to it for a more thorough perusal once you have read Chapter 4 about the implementation of an actual campaign. This might allow you to appreciate better the importance of preparing all campaign steps. Up to you.

For more details on what works, what doesn't, see the presentation of Randy Rzewnicki – a member of the SWITCH team who has given in a recorded webinar⁹. These arguments might be of interest to contact your target groups successfully.

This chapter explains details of the steps that are required to “set the scene” before the real action starts. This covers mostly the requirement to do the following – not necessarily in this exact order:

- ✓ define a clear target group and target area;
- ✓ organise a team;
- ✓ organize sufficient financial resources;
- ✓ ensure the full support from your senior management;
- ✓ build a local support network;
- ✓ organise logistical support;
- ✓ prepare information material and incentives;
- ✓ think about suitable ICT tools;
- ✓ decide on the best timing of your campaign;
- ✓ prepare the baseline survey;
- ✓ prepare the marketing strategy.

Define a clear target group and target area

Experience shows that campaigns to promote a switch from car-based to active modes of travel tend to have a very limited effect if they address everyone with the same approach. A campaign has much more impact if it is targeted towards a clearly defined section of the population.

In many cases, the selection of a target group is driven by a concrete problem. For example, if congestion levels along a specific urban arterial route reaches unbearable levels, this can be a hint to address people using this route on their daily commute. Or if obesity levels among children are particularly high you can take this as a call for action.

The specific characteristics of a well-defined target group make it easier, in a very practical way, to contact them because they can typically be reached through specific communication channels; maybe they tend to read the same magazine, maybe they meet at typical locations (to pick up something, to register for something), or they often shop in specific stores. Some groups of people also meet virtually at certain “locations” such as Facebook groups. See Chapter 4 (contact phase) for advice on effective ways to contact your participants.

Besides the decision for a certain target group you need to define the target area of your campaign. This is important because it requires quite different things if you want to address people all over your city or if you want to focus on a certain neighbourhood, on a particular office district or on specific areas that are affected by road construction works.

The more precisely you define your target group and target area, the better. For example, if you want to address “commuters” you might find it much harder to reach your target group than if you know you want to address precisely night shift commuters in a certain suburban neighbourhood.

Another important effect is, that a clearly defined target group usually shares certain concerns, needs and interests. If you know these, you can precisely respond and cater to them, which will make it more likely that your tailor-made message will be heard.

When choosing your target group and target area also consider how you can get in touch with them, what kind of contact data is available and what strategic partnerships can help you to reach your target group.

⁹ See www.youtube.com/watch?v=8WhhC1SpjDY

Organise a team

Theoretically, a modest SWITCH campaign can be planned and executed if only one single person feels responsible for it. The success of most campaigns, however, rests on the coordinated efforts of a small team. At the very minimum, the following tasks need to be planned and executed thoroughly and reliably by someone:

1. Designing the campaign, i.e. thinking through all steps at a very detailed level (see the figure on page 28). This entire chapter is about such related efforts, which must not be underestimated.
2. Coordinating and implementing the campaign. Many hands, eyes and brains are required to “leave no loose ends” and to execute all planned steps. Some of the tasks that should be included in your planning are:
 - ✓ first personal contact to potential participants (face-to-face and telephone);
 - ✓ survey interviews;
 - ✓ assembly of material for information packages;
 - ✓ shipping / delivery of information packages;
 - ✓ preparation of personal travel plans;
 - ✓ telephone hotline;
 - ✓ personal travel advice conversations (PTP talks);
 - ✓ printing and copying.
3. PR work, including writing press releases, giving interviews to radio reporters, designing and printing the marketing material, manning a stand, for example, on the main market square.
4. Evaluating the campaign to find out about its effectiveness, to gather arguments for future related activities and to find out how to improve the next campaign.

Not all of your team members have to be employed by the same organisation (e.g. a city); in fact, some of them can even contribute a few hours on an honorary basis, for example, members of a local cycling club. But even then, you will need a firm and reliable commitment from everyone involved to ensure the campaign can be carried through from start to end. And be careful not to exploit your well-meaning fellow citizens, who work for a warm “thank you”.

Organise sufficient financial resources

A SWITCH campaign does not trigger huge costs for any major physical infrastructure and is therefore always relatively low-cost. However, you will need at least some financial resources for items like the following:

1. Your own and your in-house team’s salary. This will be the major budget item but in most cases, campaign-related activities can be part of a city employee’s normal job. It is therefore not so much an issue about organising “fresh” money but more about getting approval for running a SWITCH campaign as part of the normal job description. The attached success stories provide further details about the staff resources deployed by the SWITCH implementation cities. Gdansk, for example, reported staff requirements of around 1,700 working hours by municipal staff for the entire campaign. Donostia / San Sebastián experienced that at least 70% of one person was required from the early planning phases on. A second person, contributing roughly 20% of her time, was required throughout the campaign. The most staff-intensive phases tend to be the planning phase, contact phase and the delivery of the information packages.
2. Specific mention deserves the salary for a wider support group, whose members are not part of the main organiser’s team and therefore need to be brought on board through subcontracts. For example, Vienna contracted 20 people to different degrees and for different tasks; this was the highest

contracting rate among the SWITCH Implementation Cities. In such cases, some “real” money needs to be organised so that tasks like the following can be professionally and reliably be executed:

- ✓ systematic contacts via telephone, this can require more effort than a municipal department can cover with their own staff. Donostia/San Sebastián, for example, recruited the help of two junior subcontractors to call the 3,000 people on their database;
 - ✓ conduct the baseline survey and after-engagement surveys;
 - ✓ home-delivery of information bundles;
 - ✓ delivery of PTP in face-to-face sessions or over the phone;
 - ✓ preparation of the content of campaign brochures, information material etc.;
 - ✓ design of project identity, logo, leaflet etc.;
 - ✓ bundling and packaging of information material;
 - ✓ distribution / delivery of information material;
 - ✓ occupying campaign stands;
 - ✓ professional photographs.
3. Lastly, some costs are likely to accrue for things like:
 - ✓ rewards and thank-you gifts like stickers, buttons, balloons, vouchers, football tickets, gym passes, cash rewards, credit for a bike-sharing scheme, raffle prizes etc. ;
 - ✓ costs for the creation or adaptation of ICT tools:printing costs for information material (make sure you make use of existing documents), for postcards, flyers, cotton bags etc.;
 - ✓ costs for short trips, e.g. to coordination meetings;

- ✓ postage and envelopes;
- ✓ fees for copyright protected images¹⁰;
- ✓ storage fees.

As a rule of thumb, the SWITCH implementation cities reported that they spent roughly €3 per participant on printing costs and incentives. The relatively high amount of €14,000 invested by Gdansk included the production of a dedicated **brochure**, which is widely considered a best practice example.

If you work with specific devices like card readers that are mounted on lamp-posts in a certain neighbourhood to record participants’ movements you will also have to consider expenses for the purchase or rental of these devices plus the required support. The experience of Gdansk, for example, shows that they spent an average of €8 – 10 per participant, including the costs for the tools provided by Intelligent Health for a “Beat the Street” campaign¹¹ (see page 21).

Make sure you get such expenses approved by whoever is responsible for controlling the budget. In addition, it is also often possible to find sponsors, especially for various gifts and prizes. The value of such sponsored incentives in Gdansk was estimated at €1,800. It can also be worthwhile to contact foundations who support related causes or to watch out for EU or national funding opportunities.

Our YouTube channel features the recording of a webinar about the costs and funding opportunities of a SWITCH campaign:

bit.ly/25hWwdX

¹⁰ Many high-quality images are available free of charge under a creative commons license. See, for example, www.eltis.org/resources/photos or www.flickr.com/creativecommons/ or www.vectorstock.com/free-vectors or <https://unsplash.com/>

¹¹ Also Hounslow commissioned the company Intelligent Health to deliver Beat the Street in a number of schools. The original funding from the SWITCH project only covered working with 4 schools but thanks to extra funding of £50,000 from the Public Health and Transport teams, additional 16 primary schools (+5 junior schools) could be included.

Ensure full support from your senior management

Money is not everything. In addition to financial support, you need the full backing of your senior officers and/or decision makers. This is important because you might need their advice, approval and signature at certain points. The press might want to talk to the “highest” person in your department. Some other sections in your organisation might have to contribute something sporadically (e.g. data, **press material**, layout service ...) which, in turn, might require the support from a hierarchically higher-standing body.

Build a local support network

For the success of your campaign you need partners within your organisation as well as some external institutions to create a local strategic alliance that supports your campaign. In all cases you will need the support of local political decision makers – certainly if you are city employee. To identify the most suitable non-political supporters, think about which organisations are the best ones in relationship to your target group. The roles of the members in such a local support network can vary but typically include:

- ✓ help with the recruitment of participants;
- ✓ access to contact information and (statistical) data;
- ✓ spreading your campaign message through their communication channel;
- ✓ lending credibility, importance and visibility to your campaign;
- ✓ providing pro-bono services (e.g. graphic design skills, data analysis);
- ✓ covering certain costs in hard cash;
- ✓ sponsoring rewards and prizes;
- ✓ providing information material.

The organisations in your local support network do not always have to be the usual suspects like environmental organisations. Depending on your target group, think about pro-child organisations, the local branches of a health insurance company, the local chamber of commerce, a diabetes self-help group, the labour union, a neighbourhood group, universities, large companies and many others. Also think about other existing initiatives – you could become sister or brother campaigns.

When you approach potential partners, make sure they understand the aim of the local campaign and their suggested role (i.e. delivery of data, dissemination activities, prizes). The **factsheets** can be a good basis upon which you can build your argument to convince these partners to participate. You should also emphasise that the SWITCH approach and the PTP technique are tried and tested methods.

It is also important that you can give potential partners a clear sense of their expected commitment in terms of person-hours, frequency, timing, money and the benefits they can expect for themselves (reputation, visibility and general corporate social responsibility) and for society at large (air quality, independence of older people, health of children).

Good Practice

What also helps is to provide concrete examples where external partners have made a big positive difference in other cities. You might mention the case of Vienna, for example, where the shoemakers’ guild sponsored a hand-made customised pair of shoes for the winner of a **walking game**.

Organise logistical support

In addition to the local partnership network, most SWITCH campaigns typically require logistical support for implementation where in-house capacity is insufficient. For example, if you decide to conduct your surveys through face-to-face interviews, you will need people (colleagues, volunteers, students or hired staff)

to conduct these interviews. Someone will also have to assemble the information material to be sent out, put it in an envelope, affix postage, etc. And typically, PTP campaigns always have an element of personal interaction, advice and consultancy for individual participants which require many person-hours that cannot be accomplished by just one person alone.

Most of these activities have already been mentioned in Chapter 3 – “Organise a team”. They are mentioned here again to emphasise that not all of them have to be or can be executed by your in-house team. If you have the necessary financial resources do consider to hire external support, but bear in mind the following points:

- ✓ Pay attention to national and organisational rules for tenders. An example of a UK **tender document** is available in the Toolbox.
- ✓ Before recruiting external staff, define the number of persons you need, how often and for how long you need them, what qualifications/experience they should have.
- ✓ It is important to train the **support staff** in advance. This will require time, patience and special training material.

Prepare information material and “management” documents

You will need to prepare material for both the external promotion and for the internal management of the campaign. The following bullet points describe **material** that falls into the former category, i.e. reliable, up-to-date, accurate, well-written and visually appealing information targeted to the general public and/or campaign participants:

- ✓ Facts about the benefits of walking and cycling for personal health;
- ✓ General **facts** (non-health related) about the positive effects of walking and cycling;

- ✓ a **map** showing the network of cycle lanes in your city. Make such maps very attractive. People like beautiful things that they can touch;
- ✓ a map with the network of walking routes in your city, also pointing out safe crossing points, pedestrian islands etc.;
- ✓ a geographical overview of local points of interests;
- ✓ advice on bicycle theft prevention;
- ✓ information about and manuals for apps (tends to be not very interested for older people);
- ✓ a brochure about walking at an advanced age;
- ✓ information about a local bike sharing system;
- ✓ tips about transporting children on bicycles and about safe bicycling for children;
- ✓ maps and timetables of the public transport network including multi-modal options (e.g. bicycle parking, cycle hire/bike sharing stations, car clubs / car sharing stations);
- ✓ local trains network and timetables including multi-modal options for carrying bicycles on board or park them in the vicinity of the station;
- ✓ general information on specific transport modes (e.g. guidance for bike repair).

Documents for your own internal use will come in very handy, including:

- ✓ checklists for actions in each phase;
- ✓ ideas for **incentives**;
- ✓ a list of information material to be produced.

A GANTT chart¹² could help to keep a detailed overview of the various campaign steps (e.g. page 45).

¹² There are also excellent Open Source software tools available that allow you to plan and execute your campaign timing (see for example www.projectlibre.org)

Do not reinvent the wheel! Familiarise yourself, first of all, with the existing information material available in your city, then with many existing material that is available from the SWITCH Toolbox or from other projects like:

- ✓ PTP-Cycle: <http://ptpcycle-europe.eu>
- ✓ Active Access: www.active-access.eu
- ✓ Trendy Travel: www.trendy-travel.eu
- ✓ Transport Learning: <http://transportlearning.net/index.php?id=23>

You might also find related resources elsewhere on the internet or directly from colleagues in other departments and other cities. Decide which of these documents you can use as they are, which ones you have to adapt to your own situation (e.g. city-specific facts, logos), which ones you should try to organise (e.g. from a public transport operator, health centres, local cycling association) and which ones you really have to create from scratch.

Think about suitable ICT tools

The use of clever ICT tools is one of the key elements of a SWITCH campaign. Such a tool can, but does not have to be, based on some kind of smartphone application. It can be one of the many mainstream products from play- or app-stores (low cost and widely available) or customised software (high set-up costs). Other options are **GPS watches, heart rate monitors, step counters, activity-logging websites and devices** installed by third parties, for example, chip card readers mounted to lamp posts in a certain neighbourhood that can track your movement.

Which tool you use, depends on your budget, monitoring plans, the degree of financial and technical support by external partners and obviously your target group, because the computer literacy of teenagers and older people varies a lot. Different people might have different concerns about data protection. Children might respond better to a “gamification” approach

than adults. If you work with pupils you might want to choose a tool that allows quantitative competition between classes. This also works to trigger competitive ambition between departments of the same company; between supporters of two different football clubs ... you name it. Some of these tools can even be used for a friendly competitive spirit between different cities all across Europe. See, for example: www.cyclingchallenge.eu

Just think about the basic underlying principle of what you would like to achieve. If you need numerical evidence about participants’ active mobility levels for a fair allocation of prizes, a different tool might be required than if you run a photo competition for the most attractive location that can only be reached on foot.

Examples of related ICT tools are:

- ✓ TRACE, an EU-funded project assessing the potential of movement tracking services to better plan and promote walking and cycling in cities. It also develops tracking tools to support the take up of walking and cycling measures. <http://h2020-trace.eu/>
- ✓ BetterPoints, a reward programme that can log users’ physical activity on a special app. They can then earn points and redeem them for high street rewards or donate to charity. www.betterpoints.uk
- ✓ Wien zu Fuß (Vienna on foot). An app that can count steps and converts them into reward points that can be used at participating shops and museums. It also includes a walking-route planner and a game to find hidden virtual diamonds in the city. www.wienzufuss.at/app/
- ✓ Beat the Street, a fun walking and cycling game where participants have to tap RFID smartcards onto NFC-enabled readers that can be mounted on lamp posts etc., for example, along their daily way to school. 170,000 people participated in 2015. www.intelligenthealth.co.uk

Other interesting ICT tools include:

- ✓ <http://sweatco.in/> see also www.youtube.com/watch?v=r54l8j9gIYw
- ✓ <http://goeco-project.ch/index.php/en/>
- ✓ www.walkonomics.com
- ✓ www.pactapp.com
- ✓ www.bikecitizens.net/bike-citizens-rewards-committed-cyclists/

Decide on the best timing of your campaign

The timing of your SWITCH campaign is absolutely crucial; this relates to the time of the calendar year and/or the school year, the day of the week and the time of the day as explained in the following table:

Time of year	Think about the right season where weather conditions are conducive to getting people out of their cars. Spring tends to be a particularly good time for cycling and walking campaigns, not only because of the weather but also because the habit of cycling or walking can be intensified over the summer.
Time in the school year	<p>If school kids are among your target group then you should obviously avoid school holidays. But also adults are often more difficult to reach during this time; or you reach them in atypical situations. The beginning of a school year can be a good time because this is when travel routines are being established.</p> <p>The experience from the SWITCH Implementation City Hounslow / London shows that the first contacts should be established to the school authorities at least 5 months before the start of a school term.</p> <p>Typically, participation rates drop significantly during and after school breaks; try to anticipate this in your communication strategy and don't be too surprised if it happens.</p>
Day of the week	The availability of people tends to vary quite a bit over the course of a week – almost regardless of your target group. When you try to establish face-to-face or phone-contact with your target group, think about which days of the week might be best and try it on different days. Do not call people on Sundays and be mindful that Fridays and Saturdays can also be considered holy days.
Time of day	The availability of people varies not only from day to day but also from hour to hour. This has often to do with the work status of your target group. School children tend to have a fixed daily rhythm and so do the average office workers. Nurses and police officers sometimes work night shifts and the daily rhythm of pensioners can be particularly hard to predict.

Once you have determined the ideal times for your campaign you might realise that you do not actually have full control over it because many parameters depends on external stakeholders’ schedule or availability. Be prepared to find creative solutions and compromises because a strong local alliance tends to be more important than the perfect timing.

Prepare to measure the change of behaviour (the baseline survey)

Make sure you can document the effectiveness of your campaign. This is important not only to justify the campaign (and related expenses) in retrospect but also as argument for more and bigger investments in pro-cycling and pro-walking measures in the future. The best way to provide this “proof” is with data from a before-after comparison. Therefore, you will need to record the status quo before the campaign starts and after the campaign has ended, ideally with the same set of questions.

In some cases, your city’s statistics office might already have useful information for the entire city. This is obviously useful but ideally, you should produce more specific data. What you want to know goes deeper and includes questions such as which modes of transport do your target persons typically use, at *what times, how often and for what purpose?* Or: *What level of physical activity do the participants currently have?*

All answers to these questions are called your “**baseline data**”. We provide a sample questionnaire that already includes such questions in the Toolbox. You can combine this so-called “baseline survey” before the campaign start and the first contact with potential participants to find out whether they are part of your target group, whether they are interested in further information and whether they could imagine to become a participant in your campaign.

We highly recommend that you also read Chapter 5 very carefully. It provides further information about the whole measurement and evaluation concept. A thorough understanding of this will ensure that you create a higher-quality baseline survey which returns more useful results.

In order to collect effective data in an efficient way, prepare this step carefully and think about the following issues when you design your questionnaire:

- ✓ Decide which survey methods you will use (e.g. via telephone, face-to-face, on-line questionnaire, **paper and pencil** etc.). The best method depends to a large extent on the type and availability of contact data. All methods come with specific advantages and disadvantages; think carefully about them.
- ✓ Define indicators to identify target persons. What exactly do you need to know? Age, occupation, life change situation, health condition, employer, ...? Make sure you do not ask inappropriate questions and never ask more questions than you really need.
- ✓ Define indicators to measure your success. This is important because at the end of your campaign you will want to know how effective it was. This can be done with a simple before / after comparison. Therefore, you need to know the “before” situation well. A good basis upon which you can build your survey is provided in the **Toolbox**. Depending on your evaluation objectives, you may apply only parts of the suggested questionnaires.
- ✓ Formulate your questions with great care, avoid technical language, be clear and direct to avoid any possible misinterpretation. SWITCH Implementation Cities reported that complicated questionnaires really put people off. It is crucial to test your questionnaire thoroughly in a pilot phase with colleagues, friends and a few “real” people to ensure others understand what you want to convey. Revise your questionnaire based on their feedback.
- ✓ Always include a promise to protect people’s anonymity (and stick to it!) and display a contact address where people can get in touch with campaign staff or where they can address concerns and complaints.

Besides a good questionnaire, you also need to have a robust strategy for some other practical issues:

- ✓ Organise the required technicalities (e.g. on-line tool; clipboard; return envelopes; database to store the results).
- ✓ Develop support material for the survey, such as an explanation letter, **information flyer**, “icebreaker sentence” for the interviewers, campaign contact information.
- ✓ If necessary, organise external help, possibly a call centre.
- ✓ Recruit and train staff to conduct the baseline survey. In order to reach a sufficiently large number of people, it is inevitable in most cases to get support from other people. The interviewers should understand the topic of your campaign well and should be able to answer questions and to motivate people to participate in the next steps of the campaign.
- ✓ Think about the best time to conduct your surveys (days of the week, times of the day – see Chapter 3 – “Decide on the best timing of your campaign”). The baseline survey should be conducted before the target person receives any information about the campaign’s aim and topic, to avoid influencing the result. Otherwise respondents often are tempted to provide answers that they consider to be “expected” or “desired”.
- ✓ Define a strategy for when you would stop trying to contact someone (e.g. the number of failed attempts to reach someone; seven is a good number).
- ✓ Decide whether you want to incentivise **survey** participants with something like a **sticker, button, balloon, safety vest, saddle cover, etc.**

Remember not to burden the target persons with long and complicated surveys because that may discourage them to become campaign participants altogether!

Prepare the marketing strategy

At some point it is important to inform the public about the campaign. This needs to be well prepared in at least five main aspects:

1. **Campaign identity:** Your campaign should be recognizable like a “brand”. This makes it easier to gain continued and repeated attention. A campaign logo is essential for this purpose – maybe one of your graphically talented colleagues can help. Also use exactly the same colour on every publicity material and think of a catchy campaign name and a slogan underneath.
2. **Organisation:** Think about the best time to release the information. Make sure someone is responsible and knows what is happening at all times. Ensure that someone is reachable and can respond to questions by telephone and email.
3. **Content:** Think of a catchy headline and use key words repeatedly. Develop a short, very clear and jargon-free text to be used as a **press release**. Make, obtain¹³ or buy illustrative pictures at a high-resolution which carry the main message well. Have some fun and be creative!
4. **Channels:** Think about the most suitable communication channels through which you can most likely reach your primary target audience. This can be the local newspaper, radio station, social media and a combination thereof. Your organisation’s website is also a very important medium and ideally should try to cross-link to many other related organisations. The campaign leaders in the SWITCH Implementation City Donostia / San Sebastián were able to display campaign information on screens within the local buses.
5. **Attention grabbing action:** People always pay attention to something happening “live” and literally in the street, so you might want to stage an event that grabs the attention of both the public and the media. Be even more creative!

What often helps to grab attention is if your message includes a well-known person, such as the head of a company if you are addressing employees or a local celebrity. Which person is most suitable as your local “champion” depends on your target group of course. Think of a football player, religious leader, professor, ...! Be careful with local politicians as promoters of your campaign. This might effectively reach this person’s political constituency but might make it more difficult to reach people with different political views. It also implies the risk of losing a key supporter in the next election.

In addition to drawing the attention of the main target audience to your campaign, it is also important to attract the attention of (political) stakeholders within your municipality. This might require additional measures depending on your own existing connections and can include a couple of phone calls, the personal hand-over of the campaign brochure, a special appointment with key decision makers or a public presentation of the proposed campaign.

¹³ Many high-quality images are available free of charge under a creative commons license. See, for example, www.eltis.org/resources/photos or www.flickr.com/creativecommons/ or www.vectorstock.com/free-vectors or <https://unsplash.com/>

4 Implementing the SWITCH campaign

After all this preparation, your campaign is ready to go “live”. This Chapter helps you to differentiate clearly between five phases during the campaign implementation, which are the essential steps of every SWITCH campaign. This ensures that a campaign is clearly structured, well thought through, nothing is forgotten, responsibilities assigned, etc. These five phases are shown in the following figure on the left hand side. The elements shown on the right are all part of the **evaluation process**.

The main phases of a SWITCH campaign

The main phases of a SWITCH campaign (based on Wiebke Unbehau and Sebastian Riegler, University of Natural Sciences and Life Sciences Vienna, Institute for Transport Studies)

An **action list** that is structured according to these main steps in the SWITCH Toolbox might make it easier to keep the overview and to track progress of your campaign. SWITCH project partners used the following **guideline** to plan their activity (this document is adapted to a more general format for easier widespread use).

Another very useful document which you can find in the SWITCH Toolbox is the Implementation Plan Manual "How to design a SWITCH campaign". It contains a concise overview of all phases of a SWITCH campaign and further information, for example, about which information should be provided, what lessons were learned from previous SWITCH campaigns etc.

Recruitment phase

First of all – even before the implementation starts – you have to define a clear target group that is in a significant life change situation as explained in Chapter 3 – "Define a clear target group and target area". The important next step is then to inform the members of your target group about the possibility to participate in your campaign. At this phase you might face either of two different situations (or a mixture thereof):

1. Personal contact data of target persons **is available**: You have names, addresses, office numbers, phone numbers and/or email-addresses. This means you can contact them directly and personally by mail, email or telephone. You should make use of this opportunity to inform them about your campaign, provide good arguments to participate, invite them to an information stand, ask them to return a postcard or to register at an online-platform. If you know how you can get in contact with your target persons, try to estimate how many of them you can reach by this strategy and how many of those you expect to become participants. By the way, some of the "marketing" techniques mentioned under 2) can also be useful to prepare the attention of and to remind people whose personal contact details you have.

2. Personal contact data **is not available**: In this case, you need to get creative and think about ways how to reach your target audience's attention through other means. For example, try to identify places, communication channels or situations where you can get in touch with them. Many members of your target group might (almost by definition) share certain interests: Maybe they read the same magazine, maybe they meet at typical locations or they often shop in specific stores. Some groups of people also meet virtually at certain "locations" such as certain Facebook groups. Obviously, real life is not always ideal so you might not be able to reach your target group directly enough. In such situations you have to spread your message more widely through public announcements like press releases, radio broadcasts, even conventional advertisement. Obviously, you can also try to meet people face-to-face on events or strategically selected locations.

Please note: The **Toolbox** contains a helpful checklist for organising the recruitment of the target group.

Contact phase

At this stage in your campaign, no one has yet signed up as actual participant, so you need to get in touch with them, i.e. contact as many potential participants as possible. Do not bombard them with an overwhelming amount of information. Cautiously and unobtrusively attract their attention, only to find out whether the person really is within your target group, to plant a seedling of curiosity and to invite them to participate in a short survey (see the next phase). There are two main options for establishing the first contact to them: **A) Indirect and remotely** and **B) Face-to-face**.

A) Indirect / remote contact: In all cases of remote contact, you will need to have some kind of contact information, be it email or postal addresses or telephone numbers, which can be difficult to obtain. Some campaigns simply purchase address data from a commercial supplier, but sometimes other partners can help you (without violating data protection laws) for example by providing census data, or they can send out campaign information on your behalf (e.g. combined with a partner organisation's newsletter or with its annual report).

This type of contact can be made:

- ✓ email
- ✓ paper letter
- ✓ postcard
- ✓ SMS (short text message onto a mobile phone)
- ✓ telephone
- ✓ social media (e.g. Twitter, Facebook) can also be extremely powerful if used well.

Some examples of announcement letters for this type of contact are provided in the **Toolbox**. The experience made in the SWITCH implementation cities shows, that, generally speaking, it is realistic to assume that the majority of people can be reached through SMS or Email.

B) Face-to-face contact: A completely different way to establish contact is through face-to-face encounters. This is obviously much more time-consuming but – as the experience in all SWITCH Implementation Cities shows – significantly more effective! One of the reasons for this effect might be the fact that a good number of people tends not to realise or not to admit that they could benefit from further information to a stranger or to an anonymous counterpart. However, when they encounter another human being who smiles at them, who can send and read non-verbal cues, who can move a little closer to understand shyly spoken words, some people do become aware of their information needs and start asking questions. Face-to-face contacts can include:

- ✓ generic events such as public gatherings where you can collect voluntary expressions of interest on a prepared card; possibly in combination with a sweepstakes lottery;
- ✓ group-specific events – for example, the meeting of all parents of 1st graders in one particular school;
- ✓ it is also possible to try to reach people by knocking on individual doors. This tends to be cost and time consuming but can be very effective. It is even possible to hire external staff for this purpose.

When the first contact is made face-to-face or by phone, the contact phase often comprises also the baseline survey and the motivation phase as many people are more obliged to give agreements in personal contact situations.

The cultural background and dynamic of your community is also very important. A contact strategy that worked in Spain might not necessarily work in Germany. Remember to be sensitive to social and cultural taboos, local dos and don'ts, gender roles, attitudes to children and older citizens and the presence of strangers in private homes.

Some examples of where and how to establish contact with certain target groups:

Target group	How to contact and reach the target group
School children	Through parents. A good opportunity to get their attention are induction evenings – they typically take place several weeks, if not months before school starts. Also during the first week of school, many parents drop off their children and afterwards linger on school grounds when they can be approached.
New residents	Some cities agree to send out information to the people who register their new residence.
People who have received medical advice	Waiting room of local doctors' offices or health centres. The experience in SWITCH Implementation Cities shows, that this is a particularly difficult target group to reach.
Employees of a large company	Foyer of the company headquarter, company newsletter, enclosure to payslips.

In all cases, it is good to establish the first contact with a simple message which draws their attention to more detailed information (on a flyer or a website, for example). Make sure you are using the right language; not only in terms of **writing style** but also literally to ensure that people whose native language is not yours can understand what you are trying to tell them. Also think about general readability issues, for example, large font for older people.

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Assessing your participants' situation (baseline survey)

Once you have established contact to your potential campaign participants, you should learn a number of things about them to determine whether they truly fit the profile of your target group. You should also find out some details about their current travel behaviour and physical activity level because not everyone, who qualifies in one sense, might also do so in another. For example, you might find yourself talking to a night-shift commuter, who has recently moved (i.e. someone who seems to "fit") but who is already cycling to work. In order to determine whether your potential participants really are the kinds of participants you want, you should conduct a so-called "baseline survey". This is no rocket science if you prepare and execute it carefully. Just think thoroughly about these two steps:

Survey preparation

✓ This has already been described in Chapter 3 - "Prepare the measurement of behavioural change" (the baseline survey). For your information: The Toolbox contains the baseline survey as it was applied in the SWITCH Implementation Cities.

Survey execution

✓ Announce and promote your survey through appropriate channels well in advance. This could be local media but also a whole range of allied organisations. This is important to gain attention, recognition and trust.

✓ Deliver the questionnaire through whatever form you consider ideal in your given context. If you choose a face-to-face (interview) or ear-to-ear method (telephone) make sure the timing is suitable and the interviewers are friendly and unobtrusive. An online-survey or a paper-pencil questionnaire gives your participants more flexibility but usually the response rates are much lower compared to the former methods. One disadvantage of paper surveys, by the way, is that you can end up with hardly legible handwriting, which is very problematic if you cannot decipher people's contact details.

✓ Review the number of responses after regular intervals. You can expect that around 15% - 25% of people contacted anonymously by mail will complete the baseline survey. If the number of responses is too low, you need to boost your efforts to achieve at least 50¹⁴ (better: 100) responses. This is important because with a low number of respondents you will not only end up with too few participants but your before/after comparison will also not be reliable to draw conclusions from. What is also important to bear in mind is that a good number of people typically drop out during the campaign. For example, if you have 100 responses for the baseline survey, only 80 might respond to the 1st and only 60 might respond to the 2nd after-engagement survey (see Chapter 5).

✓ Once you have collected all survey responses you should analyse them for at least three reasons: **A)** to determine whether a respondent fits your target group profile (feeds into the following segmentation phase), **B)** to describe the "before" situation so that you have something to compare the "after" situation later on and **C)** to inform the public, possibly also politicians, local stakeholders and allied organisations about the status quo.

Another intended (side-)effect of the baseline survey is that the questions typically stimulate reflection and make people think about their own current travel habits and physical activity; especially if you include some questions that trigger a thought process about possible alternatives.

¹⁴ The necessary sample size actually depends on the specific indicators you want to measure / detect. For example, if you want to detect very subtle differences, you need a relatively large number of responses. For further information consult an introductory book on statistics or consult someone with this expertise; possibly a nearby university.

Segmentation phase

Based on the information gathered in the baseline survey, in the segmentation phase you find out whether each of your target persons (potential participants) really can and should become an actual participant. You can do this easily by going through this sequence of test questions one-by-one in the suggested order:

This filtering process will allow you to identify the "low hanging fruits", that is, people who are most likely to respond positively to the campaign. These are people, who are using the private car on their short daily trips, but can see opportunities to replace car trips by walking or

cycling or who are even thinking about shifting to active modes already. A thorough segmentation process, based on the baseline survey, can help you to identify those and "tip" them over.

Figure 3 illustrates a logical sequence of filtering your participants. However, the order of these steps might require context specific adjustments, which you have to think about carefully. For example, the SWITCH team in Vienna experienced that the majority of people in a certain neighbourhood does not own a car anyway and reported that it would have been better to use the question concerning people's routine car usage as very first selection criterion.

Sequence of segmentation steps

Motivation phase

In the motivation phase, those people who would make ideal participants of your campaign are motivated to become actual participants. For this, you offer them various kinds of information materials and incentives on a so-called “service sheet”¹⁵. This is a visually attractive document like a menu of available advice, support and information such as:

- ✓ personalized travel planning talks, that are, literally meetings, where people can discuss their mobility situation with campaign staff that can give feedback on current mobility routines, advice on how to integrate active travel in every-day life and show the individual opportunities for behavioural change;
- ✓ personalised travel plans, for example a map showing the cycle paths from a person’s residence to his/her workplace, comparing travel alternatives and their impacts on individual health;
- ✓ incentives as reward for a switch to active modes of transportation;
- ✓ general maps and information on walking and cycling;
- ✓ information on dos and don’ts for cyclists and walkers;
- ✓ neighbourhood maps showing important directions, shops and service infrastructure in the direct neighbourhood with the idea to reduce or shorten trips;
- ✓ facts about the health benefit of active travel;
- ✓ information about bicycle repair workshop, cycle classes etc.
- ✓ invitations to side events to test new behaviour, e.g. test days for pedal electric cycles, common walks to explore neighbourhoods, information days;
- ✓ smartphone applications and websites that supports active travel by information and/or gamification, e.g. Step counters, activity diaries, online competitions;
- ✓ and much more, depending on your city’s and your target group’s specificities.

Experience shows that the service sheet concept is best implemented with a letter and an envelope with pre-paid postage to make it as convenient as possible to submit it. Some cities have also offered an online option to submit the service sheet, which can also work well. Of course, it is best to give people multiple options like a paper and an online version. If people, who have expressed their interest in the campaign have not returned the service sheet after a certain period remind them with a friendly letter, or – even better – a phone call.

¹⁵ The SWITCH Implementation Cities Antwerp and Vienna integrated the service sheet directly into the baseline questionnaires. This is also an option with specific advantages and disadvantages that should be weighed up carefully.

Advice phase

The advice phase is the core of every SWITCH campaign because during this stage, the participants receive the actual advice, information, material, know-how and encouragement they specifically need. This phase can be differentiated into two sub-phases:

Initial advice

What counts in the initial advice phase is that participants are stimulated to at least start and try out new mobility options, to question previously held prejudices against active travel, to familiarise themselves with a new walking route etc. It will be the ensuing “continuing support” to stabilise this new behaviour towards new routines.

There are different levels of intensity and different degrees of individual contact through which this can take place. If participants did not tick the box on the service sheet to request a face-to-face meeting send the **information packages** they ordered to the participants’ home along with a friendly letter without any further face-to-face contact. (However, with some follow up written and/or phone contact of course).

More time consuming, but also vastly more effective, are personal conversations (**PTP-Talks**) with your participants, either over the phone or face-to-face; at least if they requested such a meeting on the service sheet. Phone conversations were also tried out by SWITCH implementation cities, for example, by Hounslow. They used a team of 6 personal travel advisers to make the PTP calls from a call centre hub in order to make the volume of calls required. In hindsight, however, they concluded that this method may be significantly less effective than face-to-face meetings.

Personal, physical meetings can take place at a central location (something like a SWITCH “headquarter”, for example in a civic centre) or at the participants’ home; ideally you give them the option.

It is advisable to pre-arrange such meetings so that you or your team-members can prepare

and compile the requested information in advance. During the meeting, participants should then receive the requested material. You need well trained staff that can explain this material, provide competent answers and create a welcoming atmosphere of trust. If you are the meeting host make sure you offer coffee, tea, soda etc.

It is also important that the conversation takes place in a safe and quiet space, where a truly private conversation can unfold so that no one has to be embarrassed for asking what might seem like a naïve question. People should feel welcome to discuss any aspect of their current and possible future mobility routines which includes topics such as the best route, safety, health concerns, cultural taboos, social expectations, sweat and showers, the lack of skills, financial issues etc.

To ensure that such conversations don’t have to take place in a rush, you need a sufficient number of helpers. Therefore, engage qualified employees or cooperate with organisations carrying out the consultancy (e.g. mobility centres) on your behalf.

It is good practice to give the participants an additional thank-you present for joining the consultation directly at the face-to-face meeting. The present should be thematically related to your campaign and of interest to the participant.

Continuing support

In many cases, such initial information leads to corresponding actions. People do, in fact, often give cycling or walking “a try”. What matters, however, is that your participants develop new routines. If the new behaviour starts out as an experiment, it has to become “sticky” to the point that it is no longer questioned because it has entered a person’s auto-pilot system. This requires repetition, time, patience – and reminders from a well-meaning friend like the SWITCH team. It is therefore important to emphasise that the delivery of relevant information (no matter how personalised and glossy) must not be a one-off exercise.

You will need to retain your target group’s interest and enthusiasm during the whole campaign.

For this purpose, you can use all kinds of incentives, a friendly reminder letter, an encouraging check-up call or a follow-up appointment. Remember, that people tend to appreciate small gifts, especially when they have the feeling they “earned” them. Such incentives can be fancy gadgets like the step counter with integrated pulse monitor one on this photograph; it was given

Give-away gadget for focus group participants in Donostia / San Sebastián

as a thank you token to participants of a focus group in Donostia / San Sebastián. They do not have to be expensive things, however. They can include safety vests, saddle covers, bicycle bags, bike lamps, umbrellas, USB memory sticks, badges (children – even not so small ones – love them!), stickers, balloons and – of course – bike repair necessities (patches, tools, air-pump, etc.).

Incentives do not always have to be things or of monetary value. It can even be a free pass for a gym and swimming pool, for a climbing wall hall, for a rope parcours, museums etc. Even a match

against the local football team or a free 3-week rental of a fancy eBike can trigger motivation and enthusiasm. The more creative and unconventional, the more attention you will generate.

Good Practice

Vienna had a great idea for an incentive (actually the prize in a raffle): A pair of handmade customised shoes, donated by the shoemakers’ guild. Another prize was a 30 minute foot massage.

Feedback about achievements so far tends also to be very effective. ICT tools can be particularly helpful for this if people either voluntarily make their data (e.g. step counters) available to you or if you remind them to check for themselves from time to time. And if you provide them with information about how they are doing in comparison with other (anonymous) SWITCH participants, this can give them a real boost. But be careful, because someone who fares below the average can also be discouraged! A **collection of good examples** of ways to keep pupils enthused is available in the **Toolbox**; it also contains a good amount of inspiration about other target groups.

5 Evaluation

Once the delivery of your campaign has been completed, it is important to look back and to evaluate. This evaluation serves three distinct purposes:

- 1. Measuring effectiveness:** Assess how effective your campaign was. This is interesting for yourself but also for local stakeholders, your local support network, politicians and the general public.
- 2. Understanding mechanisms:** What were the reasons for the observed effects? Why did people change their behaviours – or only to a certain degree? What would make the effects even stronger?
- 3. Evaluating processes:** Reflect self-critically what elements of the process went well and which ones could have been better; can be better next time.

Measuring effectiveness

The effectiveness of your campaign is best measured with a comparison between the situation before and after the campaign. The most important indicator to measure is the number of car trips and car kilometres replaced by walking and cycling trips. From this you can calculate the savings in GHG-emissions and primary energy consumption (see page 42/43 "Analyse and publish the results" for tips how to do this) and the additional level of activity people gained by modal shift. These aspects are covered by the questions **Q1-Q5 and Q14** of the suggested baseline questionnaire and the questions **Q1-Q5 and Q11**. Therefore, you must design this aspect of the evaluation already during the preparation phase to capture the "before" situation by defining suitable measurement indicators (see Chapter 3 on the "baseline survey").

It is absolutely crucial that the before-survey and the after-survey correspond to each other and measure comparable information¹⁶. The "after" situation should be measured shortly after the end¹⁷ of your campaign with pretty much the same questionnaire and method that was used for the baseline survey.

¹⁶ In an ideal case, you even have data for a so called "control group", which has very similar characteristics to your participants but did not actually participate in the campaign. This would allow you to "control for" important factors that have nothing to do with your campaign but that nevertheless influenced travel behaviour in your city (e.g. a long-lasting spell of unusually good weather). When a control groups technique is not feasible, it is very important to document the possible other factors carefully and to address them in the qualitative conversations / interviews.

¹⁷ Ideally, two to four weeks after the target person went through all phases of the SWITCH campaign and had the opportunity to test new travel behaviours.

The main purpose of this 1st After-Engagement survey is to compare the data it produces with the results of the baseline data in order to identify the short term effects on people's travel behaviour changes (and possibly on people's attitudes and mind set) as a result of the campaign.

What matters in the long term, however, is whether the new behaviours still "stick" months and years after the end of the campaign. For this reason, you should also conduct a second evaluation survey about four to six to nine months after the end of the campaign. This will find out whether new behaviours have consolidated into new mobility routines. This is a good time to assess whether participants have really formed new and healthier habits. In technical terms, SWITCH therefore differentiates between a **1st and a 2nd "After-Engagement survey."** To keep the data comparable, the baseline survey and the 2nd after-engagement survey should be carried out in comparable seasons, e.g. in spring and autumn. And the questions in the 2nd after-engagement survey should be identical to the ones in the 1st after-engagement survey.

If thoroughly conducted, this method can lead to numbers that can carry particular weight as proof or evidence. Especially in discussions with politicians, stakeholders, the media and the general public, it will be helpful to have such quantitative "facts". They can also tell you whether the campaign was "worth it" – especially whether it was worth the money invested in it (cost-benefit analysis). Such numerical data can and should also be used to calculate the related reduction of greenhouse gas emissions and primary energy consumption resulting from participants' travel behaviour.

It is important that you get very clear, beforehand (!), what exactly you want to achieve. We emphasise this because it is an all too common mistake of such activities that they collect way too much data, more data than can be handled afterwards. Besides, overly long questionnaires require more time than necessary to fill in, which is a problem for both the interviewer and the interviewee. Conversely, sometimes evaluators realise during the analysis of the results that it would have been good to include another question – but then it is too late. It is therefore

important that you get clear, first of all, what exactly it is that you want to know. In other words, you need to sharpen your evaluation tools.

For this, think about what can truly tell you something meaningful about effects? For example, if you want to know how many people changed their behaviour you have to get very clear what you mean by "people", by "change" and by "behaviour":

- ✓ **People:** Do you mean all participants or are you also interested in gender and age differences? You will need to design your questionnaire accordingly.
- ✓ **Change:** Has someone who used to cycle once a week and is now cycling twice a week changed their behaviour? Just be clear whether you also want to measure the regularity of change, how often and for what distances people use which mode of transport? There are no "correct" answers to these questions. The point is merely that you/your team need to define these things in order to be able to formulate precise questions in your questionnaire that return the information you need.
- ✓ **Behaviour:** Are you only interested whether people switched from car to bicycle or also from car to walking; maybe even from walking to cycling, from public transport to active modes or any other direction? You might also want to capture the number of car kilometres that were avoided.

In essence, a good tool to measure effects is all about the precision of its components. Think also about precise indicators if you want to measure the cost-benefit ratio of your campaign. For this you need to keep an overview of all expenses and investments made for the campaign (material, staff time, printing costs – see Chapter 3 "Organise sufficient financial resources") and then compare this with the financial savings in terms of avoided costs for the treatment of NCDs, productive hours saved from avoiding congestion etc.

These three purposes require different kinds of information ("data") and different ways to obtain it. As you can see in the general overview flow-diagram (page 28), there are three components with the tick-box symbol shown on the right. They represent three steps with a so-called "quantitative" evaluation method, that is, where you count and measure things with numerical data.

Some information, however, cannot be captured with numbers; especially information that answers questions starting with why and how. Gathering this kind of "data" requires words, discussions, conversations, interviews. This is called a "qualitative" approach, represented in the diagram with the speech bubble icon.

You do not need a degree in statistics or in any other special discipline to perform a rigorous evaluation. But it is crucial to plan this important element of a SWITCH campaign very carefully and from the beginning. This section helps you prepare and conduct such an evaluation and to analyse its results.

In other words: What you need to define is what parameter exactly represents the topic you are interested in (in academic lingo this is called operationalisation)¹⁸. If you do this well, your results will be “valid”.

Please have a look at the existing evaluation questionnaire in the Annex. It will surely provide inspiration for your own city- and context-specific evaluation activities. The SWITCH project has also defined Common Performance Indicators (on the basis of the EU programme Intelligent Energy – Europe (IEE)) that can help to develop your interview guideline.

Understanding mechanisms

In addition to some information about what happened, you will surely want to know the reasons why certain effects were achieved (or not); why people changed (or did not change) their behaviours and routines. To illustrate this point, the effectiveness measurement is analogous to someone who compares the input and output of a machine. What is also interesting is to open the engine bonnet, to look inside and to understand the mechanisms that explain the effects. The type of information you need for this purpose is not captured by numbers but by words; and it can be gathered through conversations. This is a so-called “qualitative” approach, represented in the diagram on page 28 with the speech bubble icon.

The conversations to obtain these insights can either take the form of interviews with individuals or discussions with groups of people. For interviews, make sure you prepare a set of questions beforehand to ensure that the conversation is well structured. However, you should also allow people to elaborate on certain points because they might have interesting information which you did not anticipate in your questions. Proceed similarly if you conduct a so-called “focus group” discussion; this is a meeting where several participants (ideally 5-10) exchange their views live in your presence. In any case, you should get people’s written

¹⁸ And for any before-after comparison you will need to have collected exactly the same data before in the baseline survey (see section 4.4).

consent to participate, you should promise them anonymity and you should take notes; it would be even better to make audio-recordings of such conversations (interviews and focus group meetings).

You can also employ some other qualitative “data gathering” techniques. One that can be particularly effective in a SWITCH campaign is a written diary where participants record their behaviour, thoughts and experience during the campaign. You can also travel with a few selected participants to understand why they do things the way they do. Some researchers even watch video footage with travellers who recorded their trip beforehand with a mobile camera. Again, you are free to develop your own techniques that fit your specific context and target group.

By the way, qualitative information is also crucial to draw some lessons about infrastructural problems in your city. If you get repeated feedback about, say, long waiting times for pedestrians at certain traffic lights, or damaged surface on bicycle paths, you can use them constructively and send them to your colleagues in other city departments. It is remarkable how much more attentive people who recently switched transport modes are to such things compared to long-term users of the same mode, who have simply grown accustomed to such situations, even if they are really annoying.

To develop good and precise questions for such conversations think about what kind of information can provide insights into the mechanisms behind the effects of your campaign. You might have a guess about some intended mechanisms (the PTP advice being one of them of course) so make sure you include them in your semi-structured interview guide. You might also have a guess about potential other mechanisms that were not part of your campaign. For example, if there was an unusually long period of pleasant weather during the campaign phase you might want to find out to what degree this might have influenced the effects. Or did it matter that a new bridge for cyclists and pedestrians across the river opened during the campaign? Maybe you also have assumptions about other factors and mechanisms that might have mattered (e.g.

participants’ cultural background). They could help you to understand the situation in your city better and to devise more effective measures in the future by all means do include them in your list of questions you want to ask during an interview or a focus group meeting. Most certainly, there will also be certain mechanisms that you could not possibly have anticipated. For this reason make sure you also provide respondents with an opportunity to tell you unprompted things that matter in their own subjective view. This can help you discover seemingly “irrational” factors that nevertheless are hugely relevant and won’t simply go away no matter how much someone “preaches” about desired behaviour.

You should follow a systematic approach to extract the key lessons from the information you obtained through qualitative methods. If you have the capacity to transcribe audio recordings from interviews and focus groups you should definitely do this – or have it done for you. Ideally, this written material should then be analysed with a qualitative data analysis software¹⁹ and for this, you will need a so-called “code plan”, which is basically a list of topics (represented by key words) that you expect to feature in the conversations. Read through every transcript and highlight these key words at every occurrence. If you do not have a special software for this purpose you could simply open several text documents (one each per topic) and copy related statements from the transcript into the corresponding document. At the end of this process you will have all “nuggets” of your data sorted in several topic-specific documents, which can be extremely helpful to deepen your understanding of (non-)cyclists and (non-)walkers in your city. These insights will also be useful for colleagues in other departments like those responsible for urban planning, traffic safety, green space, demographic change or air quality.

Evaluating processes

Through the so-called “process evaluation” you document, measure and assess the dynamics of your campaign, the barriers and drivers encountered, the decisions taken and

¹⁹ Maybe someone from a nearby university can provide support with this.

the efforts in terms of money, staff, material and other infrastructure. In other words, the process evaluation should answer questions like: **How did it go? What went well / wrong and why? What did it cost? Who did or should have done what?** Information on the process can be derived by talking to stakeholders and persons responsible for the implementation of the campaign. Documenting the costs and resources used in the different phases of the campaign is one important part of the process evaluation. It is the basis for computing cost-benefit ratios as one important evaluation indicator.

You should also use this opportunity to look back self-critically and to document the experience so that you and others, including SWITCH campaigners in other cities, can learn from it. After all, there might be another round of a behaviour change campaign – especially if the SWITCH experience was positive. It is therefore useful to have some robust evidence about the main barriers you encountered, the key support factors, the amount and types of resources required and other aspects of managing a campaign.

Some of the parameters that allow you to assess the quality and effectiveness of the whole campaign process are probably the same regardless of where and when you conduct it. Among them are the questions of how many person-hours had to be invested and – correspondingly – how much money had to be spent. You might also want to reflect upon how many flyers were handed out and which allied organisations you managed to win for your campaign. Did pro-cycling clubs support you more / less than bicycle stores? What might the effect have been of the local election midway through the campaign? These and many other issues are obviously very specific to your city and its particular situation, political constellation, topography and climate, historical context and so forth. Prepare related questions for when you interact with the member of your team and external stakeholders in your process evaluation efforts; be it through one-on-one interviews or focus group discussions.

Analyse and publish the results

– Overall evaluation

Collecting data is not an end in itself; it is a means towards an end. Therefore, you will have to do something with the data, analyse it, synthesise it and publish it in a suitable form. This might be easier said than done because if you conduct your evaluation well, you will end up with quite a lot of data, both quantitative (numbers) and qualitative (audio-recordings, notes). It is good to have developed a data management scheme beforehand and also ideally a routine to check the quality and reliability of the data.

The main point of the quantitative analysis is the comparison between the baseline surveys and the 1st and 2nd after-engagement surveys because this allows you to assess the effects of your campaign in the most rigorous way. With the help of a spreadsheet software it will be easy to convert the essence of this data into some visual form, using bar charts, pie charts or other suitable diagram types that convey the message clearly.

When assessing certain impacts you will have to make some logical conclusions from the data you get through the survey results. For example: Imagine, someone tells you he or she lives 2 kilometres away from a child's school and used to bring the child to school by car but has now shifted to the bicycle. Think carefully what this really means in terms of car kilometres saved because one school trip could mean that the parent drove the distance twice in the past: once to school and once back home in the morning and the same double trip after school. In this example, the total car kilometres saved per day is actually 8.

Some rule-of-thumb information that might help you to calculate related benefits are:

- ✓ Fuel saved: 0,30€/km (especially a win for employers if it is a company car with free fuel card).

- ✓ Parking space saved: average parking space in Brussels' offices costs 1,500euro per year.
- ✓ Time saved: cyclist is on average 1 day of work less sick per year compared to other employees (multiply this with the average cost per work day in your region).
- ✓ Productivity & stress: cycling employees are 44% more happy & 20% more productive (Fietzersbond et al., n.d.).

The value-for-money assessment of the SWITCH campaign in Hounslow was based on the NICE ROI Tool for physical activity <http://tinyurl.com/zf2fmfe> – see also Mallender et al. (2013). Preliminary results (assuming an inactivity level of 49%) indicate a return on investment for every £1 spent over 2 and 5 years, respectively: Productivity £19.46 / £45.68. Transport £4.18 / £9.91. Healthcare £17.23 / £17.39.

For further information, especially about health-related benefits, see Davis (2014) and Kahlmeier et al. (2013) or a very concise summary at <http://travelwest.info/essentialevidence>

In addition to the impacts on people's travel behaviour "per se" it is also interesting to get a sense of what this means in terms of energy saving and a reduction of greenhouse gas emissions. To calculate this, you will need primarily two types of additional information:

- ✓ The amount of energy that is typically used per kilometre. The average new car must not consume more than 5.6 litres per 100 km of petrol. This is equivalent to 1,79 Megajoule (MJ) per kilometre. Since there are many older cars on our streets you can calculate with 2,06 MJ per km.
- ✓ The amount of CO₂ that is typically emitted per kilometre. Under current EU legislation (2015), new cars must emit no more than 130 grams of CO₂ per kilometre. Older cars tend to have less efficient engines, so for your calculation you can assume an average value of 150 g CO₂/km.

- ✓ If you also want to make statements about the time saved (from avoiding congestion) and if you want to extrapolate the effects of the SWITCH campaign (i.e. if you want to say what effects it would have if every citizen did the same kind of switch) you will need further information about average transport figures in your city²⁰. You can usually obtain this data from other travel surveys conducted in your area.

²⁰Typical data required for this kind of calculation includes:

- Modal split [% / mode]
- Mean trip distance per day [km / day]
- Mean trip distance per travel mode [km / day / mode]
- Mean trip duration [min / day]
- Mean trip duration per travel mode [min / day / mode]
- Mean speed per travel mode [km / h / mode]
- Mean number of trips per day [number / day]

6 Success stories

Antwerp, Belgium

Author: Steven Windey

General context

Inhabitants: 516,000 (2015)

Size: 204 km² (city centre with 9 districts)

Relevant geographical features: The city of Antwerp is flat. The only climbs in the city are bridges over some roads. The average daytime temperature is 7.2°C in winter and 21.3°C in summer.

Demographic structure: 13% of all inhabitants are non-Belgians, 26% are of foreign origin. The inhabitants are younger and more diverse than elsewhere in Belgium. In 2012 there were ca. 35,000 students.

Description of the city: Antwerp is a thriving city, the biggest city in the Flemish region of Belgium, with a population of 516,000 (in 2015) which represents around 8% of the total Flemish population. Flanders has 13 so-called 'central cities', i.e. cities that perform a central function for their hinterland in terms of employment, health care or education. Of these 13 central cities, only Antwerp and Ghent count as 'metropolitan' cities. Until 2030, Antwerp expects a growth of ca. 60,000 additional inhabitants. The wider Antwerp area has a total population of 1,190,769 giving the city a sizable commuter population. Antwerp hosts Europe's second largest port by tonnage after Rotterdam, with some 157,800,000 tonnes of trade in 2009. The Port is key to the city's economy and infrastructure with more than 62,500 employees. In addition, Antwerp boasts a small airport and a major train station with both national and international high-speed rail links.

Mobility- and traffic-related context of your city

Attractiveness of active travel: Antwerp and the wider surroundings are confronted with major road congestion. To address traffic issues in and around Antwerp, the Flemish government drew up the Master Plan 2020.

Large investments in all modes of transport should guarantee more fluent traffic, safer roads and a higher quality of life. The Master Plan 2020 aims at shifting half of all trips in the wider Antwerp Region to sustainable modes of transport by 2020.

These ambitions necessitate major construction works: expanding public transport networks, improving and extending cycle paths, expanding and creating Park and Ride facilities, widening the Albert canal and raising its (railway) bridges and completing the Ring Road around Antwerp.

Physical interventions were/are also undertaken to extend and improve the infrastructure for public transport and cycling: 57 km new cycle paths, 39 km reconstructed cycle paths and 4 km cycle paths with more comfort.

The city also has invested in cycle park racks (in public space and in-house) and in cycle park tower(s). In 2009, Antwerp introduced a bike sharing system with 150 stations and 1,800 bikes for 34,000 yearly subscriptions. The city is preparing to double this capacity.

Attractiveness of public transport: In recent years, Antwerp has undertaken several initiatives to promote smart travel choices among employees working in Antwerp. Hard measures include the extension of public transport by constructing additional trams lines. Also train infrastructure is used more intensively.

Car-friendliness: The city of Antwerp tries to promote Park & Ride among inhabitants, commuters and visitors. The city will invest additional resources in such facilities in the coming years.

Additional information: In response to initiatives such as the Master Plan 2020, massive construction works will be carried out from early 2016 until at least 2022. They will have an enormous impact on improving the city's transport.

To keep the city and the port accessible during the works, effective measures to minimize inconveniences are necessary. Therefore, the city decided to use these works to trigger a sustainable modal shift away from private car use to more public transport and active modes.

The SWITCH campaign in Antwerp

Chosen target group(s): Due to the ambition to tackle rush hour traffic problems in particular,

Antwerp chose commuting employees (in four workplaces) as their target group.

Timeline

City of Antwerp	2015												2016				
	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May
Recruitment of companies/workplaces																	
Launch of the campaign through road shows																	
Segmentation																	
Implementation																	
Evaluation																	
Baseline measurement																	
After measurement (short term)																	
After measurement (long term)																	

Communication and recruitment

First of all, the Antwerp SWITCH team establishes contact with the management of a workplace through telephone conversations for the initial contact to the (mobility) management. Afterwards, meetings are set up to present and 'sell' the project and to make agreements about various

details. After the Antwerp SWITCH team has obtained the commitment of the management of a workplace, we started preparing the mobility guide in collaboration with the (mobility) management of the workplace. Afterwards, we got in touch with the employees through various means:

- ✓ announcement letter about the road show;
- ✓ the road show (for all employees together);
- ✓ mailing after the road show with a request to ...
 - a) participate at the baseline survey
 - b) complete the service sheet
 - c) become a champion of the SWITCH campaign in their own workplace;
- ✓ delivery of PTP-conversations and marketing packages at the workplaces from a SWITCH info booth;
- ✓ request by mailing to participate at both after-engagement-surveys.

Local partners

The management of the companies is crucial for an effective cooperation with workplaces, employers as well as employees. The role of the workplaces (general manager, HR manager, mobility manager, facility manager, communication manager, etc.) is to ensure contact to all employees, based on templates produced and delivered by the Antwerp SWITCH team. In all live contacts between us and the employees, it is always the workplace that makes all practical arrangements and the SWITCH team who delivers the content for road shows and PTPs.

The employees were provided with workplace-specific mobility guides. These were developed in close cooperation between the workplace and the SWITCH team. The SWITCH team later delivered a PDF version of the final mobility guide(s) and the workplaces themselves arranged the printing.

Resources

In addition to the resources provided through the SWITCH project, Antwerp allocated some extra budget in order to be able to provide extra bike tool boxes for additional participating companies (beyond the four workplaces which were initially foreseen as campaign partners

Incentives used

SWITCH in Antwerp handed out bike tool boxes to employees. For each SWITCH workplace we delivered different bike tool boxes so all needs about bike repair and bike maintenance are covered.

SWITCH in Antwerp handed out the following gadgets for employees: bike saddle covers, fluorescent and reflecting backpack covers and fluorescent and reflecting high-visibility safety jackets.

A competition aspect is that the city of Antwerp makes it very visible who are the participating workplaces. The city of Antwerp gives visibility to all SWITCH partners through their website and by mentioning them during meetings with the management of other workplaces. This motivates workplaces to engage very seriously with the campaign.

In order to stimulate a high response rate to the final SWITCH survey we organise a raffle among all survey respondents with prizes such as bicycle lights, actual city bicycles and even e-bikes.

ICT tool(s) used: So far the SWITCH campaign in Antwerp did not use specific ICT tools like travel apps. Based on the experience from other campaigns, however, the city is now preparing this in collaboration with local partners. In February 2016, the city of Antwerp launched the umbrella-website www.slimnaarantwerpen.be – this site covers all initiatives (soft and hard measures) the city takes (or is planning to take) to deal with the huge challenges resulting from the forthcoming road infrastructure works.

This website already promotes a ‘smart map’, with real time info about road congestion and advantages of active and smart travel (walking, cycling, public transport, car sharing and car-pooling, Park & Ride).

The next step will be the implementation of a smart route planner (online as well as an app-version), planned in the next months. This smart route planner will be able to suggest the fastest and smartest route between point A and point B in real time. This tool also incorporates the combination of different active and smart travel modes.

Before www.slimnaarantwerpen.be was launched, the city had used the website www.noorderlijn.be about the first wave of massive road works in Antwerp. This website contains a separate section about the SWITCH campaign, which is called ‘Wijs op weg’ (‘Smart travel’) in Antwerp: <http://www.noorderlijn.be/actiepunt/39/een-mobiliteitsgids-voor-jouw-onderneming-organisatie> – the website also features an online forum where partners and citizens can leave feedback and/or ask questions and post requests. SWITCH Antwerp also delivers digital newsletters after subscribing individuals during SWITCH PTP-talks.

Evaluation

Experience with baseline survey: It is important to send at least one reminder about the baseline survey; it really helps to increase the number of respondents. Overall, the Antwerp SWITCH campaign has contacted 3,245 potential participants. 791 of them have completed the baseline survey.

Experience with after-engagement surveys: Also here it is important to send at least one reminder. About 750 participants completed the first after-engagement survey.

Experience with qualitative evaluation: Representatives from all 4 partner workplaces were invited to a focus group meeting. Eventually, 10 individuals were invited, 9 of them confirmed their participation, 3 had to cancel in the last

minute so that the focus group discussion was held with 6 participants. These people were given all SWITCH-gadgets in one package as thank-you gift.

Experience with PTP talks: The overall experience is very positive. For some individuals a PTP conversation makes a difference because it can stimulate people to think and/or act in a new way. In fact, some employees considered the PTPs as a real eye-opener.

Future plans: To achieve a permanent change of employees' commuting practices, the SWITCH dynamic needs to be maintained and strengthened in the coming years through permanent, instead of a temporary, initiatives. Besides informing and raising awareness, the city

of Antwerp is preparing a broader set of mobility solutions, including services that makes it possible for citizens to test and try mobility options. Antwerp will implement a specific approach to companies starting in springtime 2016. The first step will be a tailored and free mobility scan. Afterwards, mobility account managers come back with the results of the mobility scan and a range of possible mobility services and incentives, for employees who

are potential 'switchers'. Mobility services are for example free rental of an (e-)bike for some weeks (maximum one month). Afterwards, employees can buy their bike at a discount. Every month, the (e-)bikes will be offered to another company. The idea is to combine the start or end of the one month trial period with an event in the company (e.g. breakfast event). The first mobility scans for new targeted workplaces were organised in March 2016.

Results

We experienced that the preparation of a SWITCH campaign can take more time than one might anticipate. It surely helps to use as much as possible all relevant existing information material from all kinds of related organisations (local, national and European). Once the main information has been gathered and once the city-specific material has been produced, the campaign can relatively easily be replicated with a significant number of companies and organisations – even in parallel.

During our SWITCH campaigns, the city was already busy implementing new mobility services. To some extent, this would have required a continual update of our information material. Although this was not possible of course, such a situation signals the necessity and provides the opportunity to address more and new companies on a continual basis over the coming years.

What we realised was a particular difficulty with companies that have multiple sites across the city. Although some of these companies expressed an interest to run the campaign for all their employees and despite the fact that this would have made much sense logistically, it was impossible to produce information packages that are tailored for each site. It might therefore be advisable to prepare future campaign templates with a core section and with an easily adaptable section with site-specific information.

A positive lesson learned is the effect that the publicity about the campaign in companies X, Y and Z triggers automatic interest by other companies. This generated a number of enquiries for similar campaigns elsewhere and thus helps enormously with the recruitment of further partner companies.

Success story

Donostia / San Sebastián, Basque Country, Spain

Author: Iñaki Baro Garin

General context

Inhabitants: 185,000

Size: 61 Km²

Relevant geographical features: The city of Donostia / San Sebastián is composed of 18 districts, half of which are relatively hilly. The city centre is located in one of the flat areas, directly at the coast of the Bay of Biscay.

Demographic structure: 22% of the city population are people over the age of 65. However, most of the new residents are in the range between 30s and 50s. Immigrants represent about 5% of the whole population.

Description of the city: Donostia / San Sebastián is the capital of the Gipuzkoa province in the Basque Country. Its wider metropolitan area covers more than 485.000 inhabitants. It is an important touristic destination and this is the main economic activity of the city.

Mobility- and traffic-related context of your city

Attractiveness of active travel: The city's mobility strategy now prioritises non-motorized and active modes of travel. The city offers more than 65 km of cycle lanes and the urban cycle network is connected to the regional network and thus provides convenient links to towns in the wider hinterland and the rest of the province.

The pedestrian network has also been and is still being upgraded. The city centre is already quite pedestrian friendly and more peripheral neighbourhoods are increasingly being re-shaped in a similar direction. New approaches such as soft pedestrianisation or flexible uses of streets have been applied with the aim to recover and adapt spaces from the monopoly of motorized modes.

Facts:

- ✓ Percentage of developed land: 33%
- ✓ Index of urban compactness: 44.5 dwellings per hectare
- ✓ Public transport travels in 2014: 28,077,701
- ✓ Bicycle daily usage in 2014: 18,026
- ✓ Motorisation: 585 motorised vehicles per 1000 inhabitants (cars and motorbikes)

Attractiveness of public transport: Donostia offers a well-developed public transport service with a very high usage rate (157 trips/passenger/year) and with a punctuality rate of 97%. The fleet of 120 buses is constantly being upgraded; most recently with 11 hybrid buses and 1 fully-electric bus, which makes Donostia the first medium-size city in Spain that implements this kind of technology.

Car-friendliness: In response to the massive increase of car usage during the 1960s and 70s, Donostia started an important urban conversion programme in the late 80s to revert this trend and to create a people-oriented city.

Additional information: As a consequence of the mind-changing process, the city has one of the highest pedestrian modal shares (49%). Combined with the shares of public transport

(22%) and cycling (4%), Donostia prides itself of a 75% modal share of sustainable modes of transport.

The SWITCH campaign in Donostia / San Sebastián

Chosen target group(s): As a municipality, the target should always be the entire population. Although this aim was not realistic for the SWITCH campaign, we keep this ideal in mind for the long term. For practical reasons, we chose three target groups:

1. people who recently moved home;
2. people who recently changed their educational status (university) and
3. people who have received medical advice to increase their physical activity.

Timeline

Donostia / San Sebastián	2015												2016				
	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May
Campaign launch & recruitment process				■	■												
Baseline survey				■	■	■	■										
Delivery of service sheets					■	■	■										
Delivery of the SWITCH package						■	■	■	■								
2 nd recruitment campaign	Only for people who received medical advice																
1 st after-engagement survey								■	■	■							
2 nd after-engagement survey												■	■				

The delivery of the SWITCH package required a lot of time resources. The start of the 1st after-engagement survey slightly deviated from our original timeline, which also delayed the 2nd after-engagement survey.

It proved rather difficult to recruit people who received medical advice. Therefore, it was decided to conduct a second recruitment campaign. This second round was implemented during the second half of October 2015.

Communication and recruitment

The target group "people who moved home" could be approached thanks to partial access to a database of the Municipal Census Department. The initial contact was made by telephone. For follow-up contacts, people could choose their preferred communication mode: telephone, e-mail or post. Contacting people by

phone was very successful because this direct contact provided the opportunity to explain the campaign and to address concerns and questions immediately.

We tried to reach people who received medical advice through some medical centres throughout the city. This approach was directly made by medical staff (doctors or nurses), who were previously trained through the health delegation of the Basque Government under local project coordination control. This strategy was not very successful because medical staff did not have enough time during medical consultations to properly explain the campaign and the participation process. A second recruitment attempt was therefore made for this target group. We organized info-days in the same medical centres where SWITCH team members could support the medical staff.

Local partners

The Municipal Census Department can be considered the main local partner to reach the target group “people who moved home”. Also the Culture Diversity Department supported the campaign in remarkable ways through contributions to their Welcome Campaign; they have even already started to address all new residents in Donostia.

For the target group “people who received medical advice”, the health delegation of the Basque Government played an important role by providing access to the various medical centres.

For the target group “people who recently changed their educational status” the vice chancellor of Gipuzkoa’s campus also played a critical role as intermediary to all faculties of the campus.

Resources

In terms of our own (municipal) resources, the campaign began with an initial provision of 7 people. Two people were subcontracted to support the recruitment process and to provide assistance with the baseline surveys over the phone.

Some campaign activities required unexpected amounts of time efforts, like the delivery of SWITCH information packages. The reason was that many people could only be reached at home after specific time slots have been arranged. This required intensive coordination by telephone. Based on our experience, it could be advisable to hire external services for such tasks.

Training of staff

Our local project coordinator was in charge of training our own as well as external team members. Material provided by other SWITCH consortium partners were systematically used for this purpose. Medical staff was trained by members of the Basque health delegation, who were in constant contact with the local campaign coordinator.

Incentives used

Campaign participants were offered one out of four gifts: stepcounter, cycle torch, cycle bell or drink bottle. The information about the availability of these incentives was already communicated early on with the aim to entice people’s participation and to trigger good response rates to the service sheet.

At the end of the campaign, we will organize a raffle among all participants offering folding bicycles, “smart” wristbands and annual tickets for the city’s e-bike sharing system.

ICT tool(s) used: We prepared a mobile app to track participants’ active mobility travels based on the existent “Moves” app (www.moves-app.com). This required only some minor language translations.

The tool was offered in the service sheet and participants who selected this option were given further information and, in some cases, face-to-face instructions. Most people wished the explicit assurance that the app does not register locational data so they could be sure the app only registered distances (kilometres but not geographical coordinates). People who were already familiar with mobile apps tended to appreciate this new source of information and expressed positive feedback.

As a general observation, however, most participants reported that they prefer paper-based trip documentation. According to these signals, ICT tools should be considered as complementary tools and not as primary ones. A special situation applies for new foreign residents because a significant number of them does not initially have mobile internet connection. Smart-phone tools thus are useless for them until they own a local SIM card.

Costs

The main costs for the city were related to the human resources of the SWITCH team and some minor expenses for various print jobs. Overall, it needs to be clear that a SWITCH campaign can be rather time consuming; depending on the target groups, the required efforts can vary a lot. At least 70% of one full-time equivalent person was required from the early planning phases on. In addition, a second person, contributing roughly 20% of her time, was required throughout the campaign.

The required efforts vary, of course, over time. Peak times were during the design of the campaign, during the participant recruitment stage or the delivery of the information packages. The first contacting phase, which was made mainly over the phone, took almost two person months (3,135 contacted people) – executed by

two junior subcontracted people and by two municipal staff working at 70% of their working time. Junior level remuneration rates were €6.5 / hour while municipal expert rates were about €33 / hour. Senior expert contribution is also necessary to coordinate all tasks of the campaign and to ensure its progress.

Costs also incurred for campaign material like project brochures, incentives, a delivery bag with the campaign logo, or the final raffle among all participants. The incentives we offered were below €2 each. Regarding brochures, we took advantage of the municipal brochures that already existed about active mobility. The raffle prizes were 30 folding bicycles (€300 each), 30 activity wristbands (€30 each) and 30 annual subscription for shared public bicycles of Donostia (€45 each).

Evaluation

Experience with baseline survey: In terms of Donostia’s most important target group (people who recently moved home), 3,135 people were contacted by phone. 530 people filled in the baseline survey, by phone or e-mail.

The vast majority of people we contacted was very grateful for the information about the city and our active mobility programme. Many expressed their appreciation for the municipality’s proactive efforts

to get in touch with their new residents, especially after they had already received a welcome letter from the municipality and an invitation to a reception by the mayor. In February 2016 we started the campaign with the University with a potential sample of 2,000 first year students. Visits at each class are planned to inform the students about the campaign, and a postcard will be distributed for those who are interested in taking part in the SWITCH campaign.

Experience with after-engagement surveys:

Most of the initial participants were able to fill in the second survey (= 1st after engagement survey) by themselves because they were familiar with the campaign methodology from the initial survey. From the 530 people who initially filled the baseline survey, 490 filled the 1st after engagement survey (aprox. 8% drop off). At the time of writing, this evaluation phase was still in progress.

Experience with qualitative evaluation: In Donostia, we used two types of qualitative evaluation techniques:

1. A Focus Group session was targeted to campaign participants, who were offered an activity wristband as thank-you gift. The ten participants were recruited via telephone and covered a good balance in terms of gender, age, professional status and place of residence. Some time needs to be dedicated to a thorough preparation of the focus group and to ensure an appropriate location, moderation and documentation.
2. Process diaries were used to detect various drivers and barriers during the campaign implementation process. The target group was the campaign team itself plus some key stakeholders. These individuals reported their experience on standardised form, which was easy to fill in. The key stakeholders in our case were university staff, members of the health delegation of Basque Government and of the municipal census department.

Experience with PTP talks: People who made use of the offer of a PTP analysis were usually already aware of their travel alternatives. This meant that, in most of these cases, a rather comprehensive analysis was required to suit their needs and to find truly suitable active mobility alternatives.

The key factor in assessing active mobility alternatives for PTP participants was travel time; significantly more important even than financial savings. People's daily activities are typically so tightly scheduled that they prioritized travel time over money or health aspects.

Results

Short-term results: The difference between the baseline survey and the 1st after engagement survey shows that 48.5% of respondents have increased walking as mode of transport. 39% of respondents reported to have increased cycling as mode of transport. These figures qualify as enormous change, especially when considering the short time period between those two surveys (3 - 4 months).

Long-term results: At the time of writing, the 2nd after engagement survey had not yet been completed. However, we take it as a positive indication of likely long-term impacts that 82% of respondents reported to be better informed about walking and cycling options in Donostia / San Sebastián between the baseline and 1st after engagement survey. Likewise, 79% of respondents felt more motivated to reduce car trips and to use more active modes. This bodes well for the future.

Qualitative experience: Overall, the general sense of campaign participants was that SWITCH helps to promote active travels and raises people's awareness for the various infrastructures that the city provide. In the vast majority of conversations with participants, we got the strong sense that the SWITCH campaign successfully triggered attention to the many health benefits of active travel, both in terms of physical but also psychological health.

General insights: The SWITCH campaign confirmed our experience from previous PTP activities that a communication-based campaign can have larger impacts on modal shift than infrastructure construction which is typically seen as a bigger factor in influencing people's travel choices. What emerged as a particularly important success factor is the personal contact with participants and the fact that the "product" we offered were truly personalised to people's individual needs.

More about SWITCH in Donostia/ San Sebastián:

bit.ly/SWITCH1Qn9Xmj

The plan to launch the campaign at the beginning of the school year 2015/2016 required various preparations. Most of them needed a lead time of 2 to 4 months. The campaign itself was completed in a very condensed timeframe. Luckily, no major deviations occurred.

Communication and recruitment

The big variety of the dissemination channels and approaches increases the chances to reach every target group. The Gdansk campaign was dedicated to 3 local primary schools, including schoolchildren, their parents and the school staff. Some communication channels were used for all the groups. However, taking into consideration the age differences, they were usually adapted to children or adult participants.

- ✓ School mailing lists of parents were used on several occasions, from the announcement letter through to the reminders and "thank you" messages.
- ✓ Meetings with citizens and parents: The Gdansk citizens of those districts that were involved in the "Bitwa na kilometr" campaign were invited to a public meeting with the Mayor of Gdansk. The campaign was also announced and explained during meetings with parents that schools organise every September.
- ✓ One-to-one communication: The SWITCH campaign was subject of regular one-to-one meetings which headmasters of various schools.
- ✓ Websites: Throughout the entire campaign we were using the official city website www.gdansk.pl and Active Mobility Unit one www.rowerowygdansk.pl – the SWITCH project website www.switchtravel.eu and the website exclusively dedicated to the campaign www.bitwanakilometry.pl
- ✓ Brochures: Each potential SWITCH campaign participant received – as a part of starter kit – a brochure explaining the aims of the campaign. The brochures were customized to the age of participants, i.e. for adults and for school children ; the latter has received particular praise for its friendly layout and fun activities and was mentioned as model for similar campaigns elsewhere.
- ✓ Facebook: The campaign's profile was updated daily with news and announcements related to the "Bitwa na kilometr" campaign. It was mainly dedicated to teachers and parents. It had over 2,200 visits during the campaign lifetime.

Local partners

Intelligent Health (a UK company) provided all direct ICT hardware and software, technical support online and the first baseline survey.

Schools coordinators: Three individuals coordinated the campaign in the three respective schools, providing information, organising dissemination, distributing various material and stimulating of other related school activities.

Internal IT support:

- ✓ Setting up the online version of the service sheet and of the second survey questionnaire;
- ✓ Linking up with the official City of Gdansk Facebook profile;
- ✓ Disseminating press releases to local and national media contacts.

Political supporter: The Mayor of Gdansk (Paweł Adamowicz) and the Vice-mayor of Gdansk (Piotr Grzelak) both promoted the SWITCH campaign during the district's meetings with Gdansk citizens and participated in school assemblies at the end of the campaign.

Stakeholders:

- ✓ BlokFit, Port Brzezno (local climbing wall and rope park centres) sponsored 22 family entrance tickets.
- ✓ Mme Velo, POLAR: internet shops offered cycling / sport related products as thank-you gift for participants at the second survey.

Resources

The campaign preparation and implementation required nearly 1,700 working hours. In terms of financial resources apart of staff costs it required over €14,000 for the design of brochures or the printing and purchase of various incentives. The costs related to ICT tools were covered by Intelligent Health, our SWITCH consortium partner.

For the prizes and incentives, we found sponsors related to sport and leisure business – their contribution can be valued as around €1,800.

The campaign did not require hiring any additional rooms, call centres services or staff; apart from one person who was contracted by Intelligent Health (IH) and was in charge of the IH system maintenance. IH delivered the training about the installation and maintenance of the "Beat the Street" RFID-boxes and city staff trained the school coordinators. As we were not expecting too much interest in PTP, we were assuming we would be able to cope with the eventual interest of our target group and to provide the requested PTP information with our own resources.

All surveys used during the campaign were done online.

Incentives used

Our incentives were distributed as one of two sets; one for walking (pedometer and silicon shoe laces), the other for cycling (bicycle lights and saddle cover) (see Figure 5). They were chosen as the most adequate incentives for walking and cycling campaign and for their attractiveness for all age groups.

Competition aspects: The three schools competed against each other, which undoubtedly influenced the campaign and increased people's motivation to walk and to cycle. However, this also triggered negative emotions between adults and children of the two leading teams; manifest, for example, in various Facebook postings. It might be advisable to avoid potential fierce rivalry, for example, by building teams around particular goals, like supporting

different charities. All teams received the same amount and type of incentives that were drawn by the youngest participants as well as €300 price, sponsored by IH, for the winning team in two categories.

ICT tool(s) used: Gdansk decided to use the ICT system of Intelligent Health, which is based on electronic sensors and individualised magnetic cards. Walking and cycling activities are recorded by touching personalised smart cards (RFID cards = Radio Frequency Identification) onto electronic sensors, called Walk Tracking Units (WTUs) or 'Beat Boxes' that were mounted at lamp posts in the vicinity of the 3 schools. The WTUs send real-time data to a central database and participants can follow their progress on a website.

This system proved very suitable for the multi-generational target group. It offers game-like aspects for the children and is easily accepted by adults. The gamification of the SWITCH campaign is a very important motivational issue. At the same time, the Beat the Street system allows participants and organisers to check the records of walked and cycled kilometres.

Despite some minor technical problems all participants were generally quite happy with the system. We received many comments suggesting that this was the most motivational part of the campaign

Cost: The cost of the system was around €3.2 – €3.5 for each participant.

Time: The adaptation, implementation and maintenance of the technology was rather time consuming. It took twice as long as the "Bitwa na kilometry" game and it was necessary to hire additional staff for the system maintenance.

Evaluation

Experience with the baseline survey: The baseline survey was integrated into the registration form for "Bitwa na kilometry". Participants received the cards which needed to be registered in order to take active part in the walking and cycling game and to support the chosen

school team. The registration and the baseline survey delivered the personal data necessary for smooth implementation of other phases. Over 1900 people filled in the baseline survey which we consider a very high rate.

Experience with after-engagement surveys: We sent an email message to all participants that filled in the baseline questionnaire with a link to the 1st after engagement survey. In addition, we sent encouraging messages via Facebook and posted them on the schools' websites.

To motivate participants to fill the 2nd survey, we offered the possibility to win sponsored prizes (POLAR smartwatch, fashionable bike bags, etc.). We also sent a reminder message one week later.

Number of people surveyed in the 1st after survey: 386

The 2nd after survey was foreseen for February 2016.

Experience with qualitative evaluation: The Focus group session brought some important information about the perception of the campaign, although it was not easy to encourage the campaign participants to take part in the session.

Experience with PTP talks: We offered the possibility of individual PTP consultancy to every one of our 1,131 participants, who declared to be interested in receiving more informational and promotional material. This offer was a part of the online service sheet. We provided the choice of such individual advice via mail, phone or face-to-face. We received only 11 requests for such personalised travel consultancy; all of them were held over the phone. People were mainly concerned about those parts of their journey where there is not a dedicated infrastructure for cycling and/or for rollerblades. There were also some questions about multimodal journeys. In addition, participants who ordered the Gdansk cycling map and the SWITCH factsheet (through the service sheet) also received a link to the online calculators, with which they could generate their own travel plans and evaluate the cost- and time-effectiveness of active travel.

Results

Short-term:

- ✓ 171,383 km walked and cycled in 30 days – over 4 times the initial target
- ✓ 4,269 schoolchildren, parents and teachers involved
- ✓ 78% participation rate

- ✓ 57% of adults reported to walk more
- ✓ 29% of adults reported to cycle more
- ✓ 41% of adults reported to use their car less frequently

Long-term:

67% feel more motivated to use active mobility

Qualitative:

Quotes like to following illustrate some interesting findings from the qualitative campaign evaluation:

Krzysztof: „Thank you for the great action! It motivated my whole family to reduce the use of car and choose the bike in getting to school and work.”

Joanna: „Bitwa na kilometry motivated me to do at least an hour of intensive walking daily. My 9 years old son joined me. I must admit that thanks to the campaign I am lighter by few kilos and I also changed the diet which is much healthier now.”

Ewa: „Such an event should be organized for the pensioners, and doctors should account their patients for the completed kilometres. I'm 83 years old and I enjoyed getting points together with my great-grandchildren.”

General insights: Bitwa na kilometry was the best ever walking campaign in Gdansk. It's game-like character attracted both children and parents and enables whole families to establish new active travel routines.

Self-critical reflection

It would be useful to get broad media coverage (TV, radio) in order to make the campaign more visible. The rivalry between schools was also a bit too fierce. The questionnaire for the baseline survey may have been a bit too long and sophisticated – a shorter version could have resulted in an even higher participation rate. We could also include service sheets with the baseline survey (less spamming and a better response rates).

Success story

London Borough of Hounslow, UK

Author: Chris Norfield

General context

Inhabitants: 254,000

Size: 56 km²

Demographic structure: Half of the population is in the age group 20 to 49 years and this is the most mobile group. The area is multi-ethnic and multicultural and includes one of the largest Asian communities in London (26% of the borough's population).

Description of the city: Located on the western edge of the capital London, covering an administrative area that stretches from the Surrey borders to Chiswick in inner London. The London Borough of Hounslow is directly adjacent to Heathrow airport.

Mobility- and traffic-related context of your city

Attractiveness of active travel: The London Borough (LB) Hounslow has been working consistently over the past five to ten years to design projects that seek to efficiently target different population groups in order to promote modal shift to sustainable means. Some of these projects are related to capital investments like physical infrastructure (greenways and cycle "superhighways") implemented in areas with the highest likelihood to influence modal choice. Other projects focus on "softer" measures such as education, training and publicity. Hounslow was amongst the first authorities in the capital to develop customised marketing

campaigns promoting sustainable travel that target specific user groups (e.g. teenage girls).

Attractiveness of public transport: Alongside an extensive road network, the borough has a comprehensive public transport system including National Rail and London Overground railway services, London Underground services on the Piccadilly and District lines and 49 bus services, seven of which operate 24 hours a day. Hounslow residents in general have good access to public transport; according to Transport for London, 86.5 % of working age people can access jobs without the need of a car. This was the highest figure for all outer London boroughs (although only 21.3 % of trips are currently made by public transport).

Generally, journey times and distances are broadly comparable between the private car and public transport when travelling east to west. However, when travelling north to south or vice versa, the journey times for public transport increase rapidly compared to a car journey. Given such unequal conditions, it is clear that cars will remain the dominant modal choice in Hounslow for many years to come.

Car-friendliness: Hounslow provides most of the surface access opportunities for all trips from the city of London to Heathrow Airport and from most areas west of London into the city. As such, the geography is characterised by significant arterial transport infrastructure which suffer congestion at peak times. Conversely, the lack of suitable orbital links contributes to ongoing car dependency.

The SWITCH campaign in LB Hounslow

Chosen target group: Our SWITCH campaign targets the parents of children who are starting school for the first time. We chose this target group as a child starting at a new school represents a significant life change. Parents have to plan how they will take and drop off the child every weekday.

This is an important time to support parents to choose active travel methods, because we know that once a travel habit is established it is very hard to break. SWITCH is a campaign to establish active travel as a habit from the start.

Timeline

Recruitment took place during the summer and the active travel games took place during October and November just after the start of term.

Communication and recruitment

We set out to work with parents from 36 primary schools located all across the borough.

In order to do this, we first made contact with parents in the summer before their child starts school. Schools hold induction events in June or July where parents are informed about school uniforms and how to pay for school dinners. Our team attended these events to trigger thoughts about active travel and to get the parents' contact details.

We then followed up these parents at the start of term to provide them with additional support to choose active travel. We provided localised maps which showed popular and safe walking routes to their school and highlighted how many other parents chose to walk to school.

We then offered personal travel planning over the phone and provided local information such as travel guides and details of cycle hire schemes.

Once school had started we initiated active travel games in each of the participating schools.

- ✓ 20 schools took part in the Traffic Snake Game
- ✓ 16 schools took part in Beat the Street

The main reason for including the games was to give children and their parents a fun and enjoyable reason to start walking or cycling to school and help to establish this as a habit.

Local partners

We worked closely with all local schools and brought together colleagues in public health, education and transport from within the local authority. When delivering the Beat the Street initiative we also engaged local community groups and businesses.

Resources

We commissioned travel planning consultants to attend the induction events and to conduct the personalised travel planning (PTP). This was required as it was necessary to send 2 people to each school induction event and there were over 50 induction events in total.

We used a team of 6 personal travel advisers to make the PTP calls from a call centre hub. This was the most efficient way to deliver this element of the project in order to make the volume of calls required. However, delivering PTP over the phone presented some problems and may not be the most effective method (see below).

We commissioned the company Intelligent Health to deliver Beat the Street on our behalf in a select number of schools. The original funding from the SWITCH project only covered working with 4 schools so we secured additional match funding of £50,000 from the Public Health and Transport teams to expand the project to work with 16 primary schools (+5 junior schools).

Training of staff

We employed staff from a consultancy (JMP) who had staff who were already trained in delivering personal travel planning conversations over the phone. In addition, they received a day's training on the local context in Hounslow and details of specific local active travel opportunities.

Incentives used: In order to incentivise participation, we used the active travel games Traffic

Snake and Beat the Street. The competition element within these acted as an incentive and we also included some real incentives in the form of football tickets and free gym passes.

To incentivise the completion of surveys we used cash prizes, which were given away in a lottery format. In general, we found lottery style prizes to be the most effective use of resources.

ICT tools used: We used Intelligent Health's Beat the Street challenge as our ICT tool. Beat the Street is designed around a 'real world walking game' concept where people compete for points by walking or cycling around their local area: to work, to school or as part of a daily routine.

Walking and cycling is recorded by touching personalised smart cards onto electronic sensors called Walk Tracking Units (WTUs) or 'Beat Boxes' that are placed in and around the area. The Beat Boxes send real-time data to a central database and participants can follow their progress on a website. Pen and paper registration is provided in libraries for participants who are not online and the results were published in local press and at libraries.

As part of the challenge, schools and businesses can be invited to compete against each other to see which one can accumulate the most points. As an incentive for anyone who doesn't fall into one of these schools or business categories, a target is set for the whole town and participants are entered into prize draws with prizes donated by local businesses.

A target is set for the whole community to reach, such as 'walk around the world' or 'walk to the moon'. This format gets people's attention through a competition and involves the whole community with real time scores.

The major benefit of the Beat the Street approach is that because it uses smart cards, they can be easily distributed via schools to every child; and they can then be used straight away. This enables you to get thousands of people taking part very quickly. This is important as the power of seeing other people taking part is a big motivator of behaviour.

It is interesting to compare the Beat the Street approach with smartphone based walking and cycling games. Our experience in Hounslow is

that when we have worked with smartphone based applications previously, we inadvertently limited our user base and it can be much harder to get people to start using it and remember to keep using it. It may be cheaper initially to go with an app based approach, but if you are unable to get as many people to use it, then the cost per person may actually be higher than a real world intervention such as Beat the Street or the Traffic Snake Game.

Evaluation

Experience with baseline survey: We conducted the baseline and 1st after-engagement survey over the phone. For the baseline survey we collected 431 responses and for the 1st after survey 278 responses.

The length of the survey and the wording of the original SWITCH questionnaire impacted on response rates; many participants reported that this set of questions was too long and too complex. We also had some problems communicating with participants for whom English was not their first language.

We conducted the focus group at a public hall in Hounslow and took feedback from 9 participants. The main outcomes from the focus group are listed below:

- ✓ The campaign 'kicked off well' and the active game was generally well received by parents and children. Some suggested that the project should be built upon with future campaigns being designed for longevity and/or be continually refreshed.
- ✓ The greatest influence on participants came from friends. Opinions were mixed about the effectiveness of advertisements in social media and social media itself on influencing participants.
- ✓ Car are still considered necessary for longer journeys, trips with heavy objects (e.g. bulk shopping) or during heavy rain.
- ✓ Walking generated the most positive emotions for participants when compared to other travel modes.

- ✓ Participants had safety concerns regarding cycling in the local area and across London. Parents were more risk averse to cycling since having children.

- ✓ Walking to school helped to create a 'bond' between parents and children.
- ✓ The resource packs of printed materials (in particular the "Walk to School Map") were much appreciated.

Results

The Hounslow SWITCH campaign exceeded targets for participation by local people. We worked with 36 primary schools, we made contact with over 1,000 parents of children starting school for the first time and delivered 400 PTP sessions to car users.

We delivered the Traffic Snake Game in 20 schools and Beat the Street in 16 primary schools (and 5 junior schools). Over 11,000 people took part in the Beat the Street campaign and collectively they walked and cycled over 39,000 miles (more than 1.5 times around the world!)

The most commonly reported main benefits of Beat the Street were feeling more fit and healthy, having fun and exploring the local area. Eight out of ten people thought that Beat the Street helped them to be more active and to feel healthier. Half of all respondents said Beat the Street helped them travel by car less often.

Reflection

When we run the campaign next year we plan to do more engagement with parents in the two weeks before term starts. We will also bring forward the active travel games into September. This is to allow more time before the clocks go back and the weather starts to get worse.

Quotes from participants about health benefits:

"Beat the Street helped me become more active. Ensuring I left my car at home where possible. It brought my family together."

"Encouraged me to walk more and that helped me in controlling my blood sugar levels well."

"I got more exercise because I walked and I travelled on foot to places just for fun and to collect points. I didn't see walking as exercise and I thought exercise was boring but I was wrong about both things."

Quotes from participants about changing travel modes:

"It made me realise how close places are to walk, whereas before we would have automatically jumped in the car."

"It made me want to walk from Feltham Station to home and not get the bus."

Quotes from participants about social benefits:

"As a family we felt closer to the community as all the kids and family in our neighbourhood were also doing Beat the Street. As parents we bonded with the kids and had a 'purpose' while walking and the kids enjoyed it big time."

"I spent extra time with my family. We specially went outside on weekends just to touch our card."

Success story

Vienna, Austria

Authors: Wiebke Unbehaun, Yasmin

Stoderegger, Mailin Gaupp-Berghausen

General context

Inhabitants: 1.8 million

Size: 415 km²

Relevant geographical features: Vienna is located on a relatively flat plain in north-eastern Austria. Daily average temperatures reach a maximum of 33 degrees and at a minimum of 10 degrees below zero with medium precipitation rates of 40-60 mm during the summer and 20- 40 mm during the winter.

Demographic structure: Vienna's current population is around 1.84 million and is predicted to rise to 2 million by 2030. Currently, about 25% of the population is older than 64. About 11% of the population are students and 37% have a migrant background. The unemployment rate lies at approximately 11.6%.

Description of the city: Thanks to its rich cultural heritage, its high liveability, vibrant streets and public spaces, Vienna is a great city for walking and cycling. To increase its cycle and walking friendliness the city hosted the Velo-City conference in 2013, the Walk21 in 2015 and it also proclaimed 2015 as the "Year of Walking". The increasing population rate is accompanied by a decreasing car ownership rate over the last couple of years. The modal split of all journeys is: 27% by car, 39% by public transport, 27% walking and 6% cycling. Increasing the use of cycling and walking is possible due to the comparatively low average car trip length of 7.6 km with an average travel duration of 32 minutes.

Mobility- and traffic-related context

Attractiveness of active travel: Key of the city's strategy to support active travel was the expansion of infrastructures for cycling and walking. Vienna currently offers 1,270 kilometres of cycle lanes. Cyclists are also allowed to use one-way streets in the opposite direction on about 238 kilometres of one-way streets. The infrastructural changes are expected to enable a growth of cycling from 7% in 2015 to 10%. As the modal split of the city shows, walking is already very popular (27%). The major motivational pull factors in favour of walking are the nice surroundings of the pathways and the simplicity of this travel mode.

Attractiveness of public transport: The public transport system in Vienna is very well developed. The major subway and tramway lines run every three to five minutes during peak-times. Public transport has a share of 39% of the modal split.

Car-friendliness: Car availability in Vienna is relatively low. Only 27% of trips of Vienna's inhabitants are made by car with a decreasing tendency. Recent data shows that 14.5% of all trips between 1 and 2 kilometres are made by car. 14% of the total city's area is dedicated to traffic infrastructures.

The SWITCH campaign in Vienna

The SWITCH campaign in Vienna ran from spring to autumn 2015.

Chosen target groups: At the most basic level, Vienna's target group are people who make short car journeys that can be realistically replaced by

walking or cycling trips. The SWITCH campaign focussed on people who have access to a car and have recently moved houses, who received medical advice to increase their physical activities and had another life change moment (which was captured during the contact phase).

Timeline

City of Vienna	2015												2016				
	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May
Preparation and communication	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
Recruitment and contacting people	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
Baseline survey				■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
Motivation phase				■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
Consultancy and service phase					■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
Integration of ICT in the campaign					■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
1 st after-engagement survey								■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
Focus group										■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
2 nd after-engagement survey											■	■	■	■	■	■	■

Primarily, a dense campaign run time of two month was foreseen. Adaptation in the timeline became necessary because of difficulties with the collection of contact data from the target groups. Therefore, the period of contacting people and doing the baseline survey took longer than originally expected. To ensure the defined intervals between the baseline and the two after engagement survey for each single person made it necessary to manage all three surveys simultaneously for a certain period of time.

Communication and recruitment

To make people interest in the campaign and to contact same several tailored communication strategies were followed. The contact to people who recently moved houses was established through real estate developers, neighbourhood associations, specific events such as the Smart

Citizen Labs, face-to-face interviews at new housing projects, as well as through address data provided by the Austrian postal service and university mailing lists. For other groups face-to-face contact was also established in leisure and recreation areas, like parks, public events and open air swimming pools.

Due to privacy concerns, the group of people who recently received medical advice to increase their physical activity level appeared to be a hard-to-reach group. No contact data of those people could be obtained. Therefore, partnerships with different doctors, hospitals and Health centres were established and announcement postcards were disseminated. In order to reach more people, weekly get-togethers of Nordic Walking groups of elderly people were visited as well as specific public events such as the "Viennese Diabetes Day" or the "Experience" exhibition for active elderly.

This active approach to reach the target groups was crucial for the success of the campaign. We also ensured that a broad range of communication channels could be used, including email, SMS text messages, calling of a hotline number, return of postcard free of charge, online through our websites or via a QR-Code.

Local partners

The Mobility Agency for the City of Vienna was the key partner in our campaign. The SWITCH campaign was embedded in the action "Year of Walking". So the SWITCH campaign benefited from comprehensive material and incentives for the information packages; It also provided resources for PTP talks and bike repair workshops.

From the health sector the campaign received also broad support. The Vienna Regional Health Insurance Fund promoted SWITCH within the scope of their "Smokers-Hotline".

In addition to a huge number of doctors, hospitals and health care centres, the Viennese Housing Service and some real estate developers were also involved to support the contact to the target persons.

Resources

We employed staff to recruit participants, to conduct the interviews, to prepare and deliver information bundles and to conduct the PTP talks. In total, more than 20 different people were employed to different degrees and for different tasks.

All staff was trained by the core SWITCH team with the help of a comprehensive guideline for the interviews and with a detailed presentation

of SWITCH. Two training sessions were necessary to get all 20 support staff up to speed. Four of them received extra training from the Mobility Agency Vienna to conduct the PTP talks. An important factor of success was that the involved staff highly agreed to the idea of active travel and the reduction of short car trips.

Incentives used

We organised a raffle with different prizes, including a bicycle, a premium trolley, step counters, umbrellas etc. These incentives were used to motivate people to register for the campaign and to stay in all three surveys. Other incentives were offered on our Service Sheet and were handed out during certain events; for example multifunctional scarfs, bike saddle covers, shoelaces with instructions, reflecting snap bands. The personal delivery of those incentives was very effective to motivate the participants to stick to the campaign. However, such a personal delivery service was a significant logistical challenge.

Competition aspects: The target groups did not compete with each other in any way. In our view, participants were genuinely motivated by the face-to-face contacts with campaign staff, by their interest in the various benefits of active travel and the information provided. The PTP talks and the bike repair workshops provided very concrete know-how and thus seemed particularly effective to motivate participation. This has been confirmed by sample interviews with participants.

ICT tools used: Different ICT tools were used during the campaign. The project partner Mobility Agency Vienna developed the app "Wien zu Fuß" (Vienna on foot), which included a step counter and a treasure hunt game for Vienna's "Year of Walking" campaign. In addition, we also promoted the app "AnachB" (AtoB) and a SWITCH-tailored version of the Moves app, which connects to the Moves API and uploads the users' activity data to the SWITCH server.

Especially young people who found conventional paper maps inconvenient were interested in different ICT technologies. Also the opportunity to win prizes was an important factor to participate and to increase the daily amount of physical activity.

Evaluation

Experience with baseline survey: In order to promote the campaign 20,600 registration postcards and about 10,000 announcement letters were distributed through various channels. 1,540 people completed the baseline survey; 863 during face-to-face interviews, 508 by phone and 168 registered at our online platform. 957 of all respondents were interested personalised information material; altogether they ordered 3,743 pieces of information material.

Experience with after-engagement surveys: The 1st after-engagement survey was completed by 692 people and the 2nd after-engagement survey by 417 people. Most of the questionnaires were answered by phone.

Experience with qualitative evaluation: The qualitative evaluation was conducted through a focus group meeting, to which we invited 12 participants; 7 of them attended. We took care to create a welcoming atmosphere for all participants so that they felt comfortable and safe to express their opinions openly; including critical observations. We offered also an incentive of €30 and some smaller give-aways. Participants appreciated the opportunity to share their views.

Experience with PTP talks: The PTP consultancy was performed by four staff members, distributed to four stations with specific personalised information on travel and health. The effort to attract people to this special service was rather high when compared to the number of people who actually showed up for the PTP talks.

Results

General insights could be gained at how a campaign in Vienna can be organized. It became obvious that conducting a SWITCH campaign in a city like the City of Vienna with an already low car usage rate and an excellent public transport system requires tailored strategies for identification and recruitment. The areas of the city the campaign was addressed to was carefully chosen. Various communication channels were offers to cover the diversity of the target group and to make people interest. In total, more than 3,700 different maps and brochures on active travel were requested by the SWITCH participants. The most popular ones were different maps, like the Vienna walking and cycling maps. The most preferred incentive was the multifunctional scarf which had a strong context to walking and cycling.

To measure the impact of the SWITCH campaign, participants were contacted again a short term and about five months after the campaign. They were asked different questions regarding their travel behaviour. In total, 692 people answered the 1st after-engagement survey, consisting of 525 people who received information material and 167 people who didn't requested information material and referred as a control group. Within the group of people who received information material an increase of more than 4% of additional monthly general walking trips was reported.

In contrast, a decrease of more than 5% of monthly general walking trips was reported by the control group. Further, the percentage increase of additional monthly cycling trips was higher within the group of people who received free information material.

However, the most important changes were reached regarding the general travel behaviour of people who use the car as drivers for all their trips: whereas, a decrease of 4.27% of monthly trips was reported within the group of people with information material. For the same period the control group reported an increase of 12.47% additional monthly car trips. In addition, people who received information material stated that they feel better informed about walking and cycling and the benefits of active travel now.

They have talked more often to friends about the SWITCH campaign, and are more motivated to reduce car trips and travel by active modes due to the campaign than people who were not interested in receiving free information material.

The latest modal split data for the end of the year 2015 proved the success of all combined actions on active travel in the City of Vienna. An increase of one percent of the share of walking trips in the modal split of Vienna's inhabitants was reached.

Self-critical reflection

We faced many challenges during the implementation of the campaign. Despite strong efforts, some tools and actions were not as successful as anticipated. Others, such as the face-to-face interviews, were very successful. The admittedly very time consuming face-to-face approach resulted in one third more participants than the telephone surveys. Thanks to our experience from other projects, thanks to the support from our project partners, the local stakeholders and the strong efforts of our

interviewers and campaign management 1,540 people filled in the baseline survey in the end; 957 of them expressed interest in and received various information bundles and thus became participants of the SWITCH campaign. But even those who did take part in the personalised travel planning process showed positive agreement by taking part in one or two further surveys after the first contact.

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7 The SWITCH Toolbox

Documents such as those mentioned below are available in the SWITCH online Toolbox at www.polisnetwork.eu/switch

Disclaimer: Despite a very thorough quality assurance procedure, we provide all documents in the Toolbox without any claim for completeness, accuracy or legal liability. Do not use them without checking and adapting their content very carefully and use them entirely at your own risk.

	Publicity material	For stakeholders & partners	For potential participants	Trainers / execution partners	For actual participants	For internal use
Recruitment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Health arguments for different target groups ✓ Factsheet on Cycling, Walking and Health ✓ Interview on Cycling and Health ✓ Press releases ✓ Ideas for incentives / giveaways 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ PTP-Cycle methodology for different target groups ✓ PTP-Cycle Training Manual 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Advice to be more active ✓ Examples of incentives ✓ Info material ✓ Examples of maps ✓ Brochure to motivate schoolchildren 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Recruitment template ✓ Guideline PTP template (short version) ✓ Roadmap for a SWITCH campaign ✓ Factsheets from SWITCH Implementing Cities ✓ Video interview: The SWITCH approach ✓ Video interview: The SWITCH campaign in Gdansk ✓ Transferability analysis ✓ Sample tender for external support
Implementing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Information Flyer 					
Evaluation		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Baseline survey ✓ After-engagement survey ✓ Questions for semi-structured interviews ✓ Focus group (moderation and transcription tips) 				
ICT usage		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Ideas for existing apps ✓ "Beat the street" system ✓ Ideas for customised and non-customised ICT tools 				
Results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Articles ✓ Press releases 					

Guideline for Personalised Travel Planning

1 Recruitment Phase

Choose of target group / target persons

SWITCH basics for local campaigns:

- ✓ In general: people using the private car at least sometimes.
- ✓ In specific: defined target group from the application form and/or first training seminar.

Lessons learned from SWITCH

It can be an advantage to choose a clear defined area of your city, where high success is expected.

Get contact data of target persons

SWITCH basics for local campaigns:

Personal contact and address data is needed information to be provided for local campaigns.

- ✓ How do you intend to approach the contact persons?
- ✓ How do you intend to get the address data (including telephone numbers)?
- ✓ What partners do you need and how do you convince them to support you?
- ✓ What steps will you undertake to get into personal contact?

2 Contact Phase

Send announcement letter

SWITCH basics for local campaigns:

- ✓ Announcement of campaign and of the telephone contact later on by an official letter to addresses of target persons;
- ✓ Information to be provided for local campaigns;
- ✓ Who is the right person to sign the letter/to promote campaign?
- ✓ What kind of distribution channels will you apply?

NOTES

Lessons learned from SWITCH

Be aware that it should be a trustworthy and almost neutral person; if possible there should be no segmentation by political parties etc. The choice of person may depend on the area or topic chosen for campaign.

3 Motivation

Prepare information material

SWITCH basics for local campaigns:

List of material, Local information (provided by city) e.g.:

- ✓ Cycling and walking maps;
- ✓ Neighbourhood maps;
- ✓ Information on dos and don'ts for cyclists and walkers;
- ✓ Better health by active travel;
- ✓ General information provided by the SWITCH project (i.e. factsheets about walking, cycling, health).

Information to be provided for local campaigns

- ✓ What are the expected information needs of target persons?

- ✓ Name what information is available and to what extent!
- ✓ Do you plan to provide new information and does it have to be printed, published etc.?
- ✓ Who can provide additional information?
- ✓ Who stores the information material and where?

Lessons learned from SWITCH

What is the state of knowledge and the state of distribution of information in the city? How to distribute something "new, they do not know yet" to the target person?

Be aware that storing information material and incentives need some space.

NOTES

Send out service sheet

SWITCH basics for local campaigns:

- ✓ Offering information, personal consultancy (and incentive).

Information to be provided for local campaigns:

- ✓ What are the best distribution channels in your city?
- ✓ Which will you apply?
- ✓ How will you distribute the service sheet (mail, email or personal hand over at doors, events etc.)?

Lessons learned from SWITCH
Professional design, readability, accessibility

Incentives

SWITCH basics for local campaigns:

- ✓ Incentives to motivate and endorse the behaviour offered in the service sheet and/or during the contact phase to convince persons to register on a platform and to become participants of the campaign etc.

Information to be provided for local campaigns:

- ✓ What are the best distribution channels in your city?
- ✓ Which will you apply?
- ✓ How will you distribute the service sheet (mail, email or personal hand over at doors, events etc.)

Lessons learned from SWITCH
Professional design, readability, accessibility

NOTES

4 Consultancy

Service sheet / Service phase

SWITCH basics for local campaigns:

- ✓ Return of service sheet. People who did not send the service sheet back are contacted by mail or phone to remind them they still need to answer or to answer the service sheet directly.

Information to be provided for local campaigns:

- ✓ Who is collecting the service sheets?
- ✓ Who is doing the reminder calls/letters and emails?
- ✓ Who asks the participants to complete the service sheet by phone?

Lessons learned from SWITCH

Reminder one to two weeks after sending the service sheet by mail, one week after sending it by email.

If the participants do not send the completed service sheet, offer them the opportunity of telling their information needs in a phone call.

Arrange information material

SWITCH basics for local campaigns:

- ✓ Arrange personalised information packages.

Information to be provided for local campaigns:

- ✓ Who will arrange the information material to personalised packages geared to the service sheet?
- ✓ Are you using own existing staff or do you need additional staff?

Lessons learned from SWITCH

Staff needs to be reliable but not highly qualified. More crucial is to have enough staff and time for that. Be aware that sorting and string information material and incentives need some space.

NOTES

Distribute information bundles

SWITCH basics for local campaigns:

- ✓ Personal delivery Personalised information packages.

Information to be provided for local campaigns:

- ✓ Who will distribute the information material to personalised packages geared to the service sheet?
- ✓ Are you using own existing staff or do you need additional staff?

Lessons learned from SWITCH

Distribution should take place as soon as possible after receiving the service sheet back.

Distributing person has to have comprehensive knowledge, must be trustworthy and must be able to give reliable information and consultancy.

Check whether a mobility agency/association can provide experienced staff.

Appointments for personal consultancy

SWITCH basics for local campaigns:

- ✓ Personal consultancy is offered, when asked for in the service sheet. Appointment for this consultancy talks has to be fixed with the participant.

Information to be provided for local campaigns:

- ✓ Who is arranging the appointments?

Lessons learned from SWITCH

Appointments should be fixed shortly after receipt of the service sheet

Personal consultancy

SWITCH basics for local campaigns:

- ✓ Personal consultancy is offered, when asked for in the service sheet. Visits at the participants' houses take place. Alternatively counselling interviews can take place at a consultancy office.

Information to be provided for local campaigns:

- ✓ Who is doing the personal consultancy?

Lessons learned from SWITCH

Consulting person has to have comprehensive knowledge, must be trustworthy and must be able to give reliable information and consultancy.

Check whether a mobility agency/association can provide experienced staff.

NOTES

5 Test new behaviour and further motivation, supplement measures

SWITCH basics for local campaigns:

- ✓ Encourage people to test and enjoy new behaviour.

Information to be provided for local campaigns

- ✓ What do you intend to do to encourage persons to test new behaviour?

Lessons learned from SWITCH

There are many examples available from other projects:

RTF System with games and competitions (IH), Apps to track behaviour and measure positive effect (moves, etc.),

Test rides with private or with hire cycles, events, competitions.

NOTES

SWITCH Pre-engagement survey (Baseline)

In black – core questions on travel behaviour

In green - core questions for segmentation and stages of change

In red – core questions on mode availability

In purple – core questions on health

In grey – optional questions on health

In blue – core questions on persons and households attribute

Promise about privacy protection! (Your contact data and any other information about you will only be used for the SWITCH campaign. Under no circumstances will we disclose this data to anyone outside the SWITCH team. Upon your written request (insert contact details of the SWITCH team) we will delete all such data about you. Please sign below to indicate that you agree to these conditions.)

Q1 – How many days a week do you in general commute to work /university? (Please tick the numbers of days!)

Number of days	Not applicable (do not ask Q2 to Q4)
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Q2 – What is the distance between your origin-address and your workplace/school/university (single trip, door to door-distance)?

Kilometers
km; m

Q3 – How many minutes does it takes you (single trip, door to door-distance)?

Minutes
min

Q4 – On average, how many days a week do you travel to work/school/university using the following modes (Please tick boxes in the table below!)

	Never	1 day a week	2 days a week	3 days a week	4 days a week	5 days a week
Walking						
Cycling						
Public Transport						
Car/Motorcycle as driver						
Car/Motorcycle as passenger						

Thinking about all your trips during the week ...

Q5 - How often do you use each of the following modes of travel for all your trips, e.g. to the shops, work, school, university, to friends, or all other places you visit?

	Daily or almost daily	4-5 days per week	1-3 days per week	1- 3 days per month	Less than once per month	Never or almost never	Unknown
Walking							
Cycling							
Public Transport							
Car/Motorcycle as driver							
Car/Motorcycle as passenger							

Q6 - Which of the following statements best describes how you feel about your current level of car use for daily trips and whether you have any plans to try to reduce some or all of these car trips? (Please choose which statement fits best to your current situation and tick only one box!)

At the moment I use the car for most of my trips. I am happy with my current level of car use and see no reason why I should reduce it.	
At the moment I do use the car for most of my trips. I would like to reduce my current level of car use, but feel at the moment it would be impossible for me to do so.	
At the moment I do use the car for most of my trips. I am currently thinking about changing some or all of these trips to non-car modes, but at the moment I am unsure how I can replace these car trips, or when I should do so.	
At the moment I use the car for most of my trips, but it is my aim to reduce my current level of car use. I already know which trips I will replace and which alternative transport mode I will use, but as yet have not actually put this into practice.	
As I do not own / have access to a car, reducing my level of car use is not currently an issue for me.	
As I am aware of the many problems associated with car use, I already try to use non-car modes as much as possible. I will maintain or even reduce my already low level of car use in the next months.	

Q7 - Over the last 12 months have you done more walking or cycling for everyday travel than in previous years? (Multiple answers are possible)

Yes, more walking	Yes, more cycling	No
-------------------	-------------------	----

Q8 - Do you intend to do more walking or cycling in the future? (Multiple answers are possible)

Yes, more walking	Yes, more cycling	No
-------------------	-------------------	----

Q9 - Would you like to receive free information material and personal advice on the use of active modes of travel like walking and cycling like walking and cycling and the benefits for your health?

Yes	No
-----	----

Q10 - Do you have at least one properly functioning bicycle? (Please tick one box!)

Yes	No
-----	----

Q11 - Do you have a driving license for a car? (Please tick one box!)

Yes	No
-----	----

Q12 - Do you have access to a car or van? (Please check one box!)

Never	Sometimes	Always
-------	-----------	--------

Q13 - Do you have any annual/monthly/weekly ticket for public transport?

Yes (please specify)			No
annual	monthly	weekly	

Q14 - In the last seven days, how many days have you done 30 minutes or more of physical activity, which was enough to raise your heart rate and breathing rate? This may include sport, exercise, brisk walking, cycling or housework. The 30 minutes do not have to be done all at once, but one episode should last at least 10 minutes.

0 days	1 day	2 days	3 days
4 days	5 days	6 days	7 days

Q15.1 - Regular cycling or walking for everyday travel is a good thing to do for improving health.

I strongly disagree	
I partly disagree	
I partly agree	
I strongly agree	
I don't know / I don't have an opinion	

Q15.2 - Physical activity helps prevent chronic diseases like cardiovascular diseases, diabetes, cancer, as well as strengthening mental health and bones.

I strongly disagree	
I partly disagree	
I partly agree	
I strongly agree	
I don't know / I don't have an opinion	

Q15.3 - For children and their health it is important they are physically active for at least 60 minutes every day.

I strongly disagree	
I partly disagree	
I partly agree	
I strongly agree	
I don't know / I don't have an opinion	

Q16 - Please state the following information about you and your household

Year of Birth		
Gender	female	male

Q17 - What is your highest level of education? (Please check only one box!)

No graduation	
Lower secondary education	
Upper secondary education	
Post-secondary education non-tertiary education	
Short-cycle tertiary education	
Bachelor or equivalent	
Master or equivalent	
Other	

Q18 - Please state the number of persons living in your household (including yourself).

Number of persons aged under 6 years	
Number of persons aged between 6 and 17 years	
Number of adults	

Thanks

A short "thank you" to the respondents and your contact data.

Q19 - We would like to get in touch in about one month to see if you made some changes after participating in the SWITCH-Campaign. Please type your email address here:

e-mail:

If you have any concerns about this questionnaire, the use of your data or if you would like to file a complaint about any aspect of this survey please contact ...

SWITCH After-engagement survey (1 and 2)

In black – core questions on travel behaviour

In green - core questions for segmentation and stages of change

In red – core questions on mode availability

In purple – core questions on health

In grey – optional questions on health

In orange – core/optional (tbd) questions on campaign success

In blue – core questions on persons and households attribute

Q1 – How many days a week do you in general commute to work /university? (Please tick the numbers of days!)

Number of days	Not applicable <i>(do not ask Q2 to Q4)</i>
----------------	--

Q2 – Is the address of your worksite/School/University still the same since our last conversation?

Yes <i>(do not ask Q2.1 to Q2.2)</i>	No	Not applicable <i>(do not ask Q2.1 to Q2.2)</i>
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If No: Q2.1 – What is the distance between your origin-address and your new workplace/school/university (single trip, door to door-distance)?

Kilometers

If No: Q2.2 – How many minutes does it takes you (single trip, door to door-distance)?

Minutes

Q3 – On average, how many days a week do you travel to work/school/university using the following modes (Please tick boxes in the table below!)

	Never	1 day a week	2 days a week	3 days a week	4 days a week	5 days a week
Walking						
Cycling						
Public Transport						
Car / Motorcycle as driver						
Car / Motorcycle as passenger						

Thinking about all your trips during the week ...

Q4 - How often do you use each of the following modes of travel for all your trips, e.g. to the shops, work, school, university, to friends, or all other places you visit?

	Daily or almost daily	4-5 days per week	1-3 days per week	1- 3 days per month	Less than once per month	Never or almost never	Unknown
Walking							
Cycling							
Public Transport							
Car / Motorcycle as driver							
Car / Motorcycle as passenger							

Q5 - Since the last survey do you travel by the following modes more often, less often or just the same?

Walking	Stayed the same	
	More often	
	Less often	
Roughly how many trips and how many minutes more per week do you walk more often?		
Approximate number of trips more per week		
Approximate number of minutes more per week		
Cycling	Stayed the same	
	More often	
	Less often	
Roughly how many trips and how many minutes more per week do you cycle more often?		
Approximate number of trips more per week		
Approximate number of minutes more per week		
Public transport	Stayed the same	
	More often	
	Less often	
Roughly how many trips and how many minutes more per week do you travel by public transport more often?		
Approximate number of trips more per week		
Approximate number of minutes more per week		
Car / Motorcycle	Stayed the same	
	More often	
	Less often	
Roughly how many trips and how many minutes more per week do you travel by car more often?		
Approximate number of trips more per week		
Approximate number of minutes more per week		

Q6 - Which of the following statements best describes how you feel about your current level of car use for daily trips and whether you have any plans to try to reduce some or all of these car trips? (Please choose which statement fits best to your current situation and tick only one box!)

At the moment I use the car for most of my trips. I am happy with my current level of car use and see no reason why I should reduce it.	<input type="checkbox"/>
At the moment I do use the car for most of my trips. I would like to reduce my current level of car use, but feel at the moment it would be impossible for me to do so.	<input type="checkbox"/>
At the moment I do use the car for most of my trips. I am currently thinking about changing some or all of these trips to non-car modes, but at the moment I am unsure how I can replace these car trips, or when I should do so.	<input type="checkbox"/>
At the moment I use the car for most of my trips, but it is my aim to reduce my current level of car use. I already know which trips I will replace and which alternative transport mode I will use, but as yet have not actually put this into practice.	<input type="checkbox"/>
As I do not own / have access to a car, reducing my level of car use is not currently an issue for me.	<input type="checkbox"/>
As I am aware of the many problems associated with car use, I already try to use non-car modes as much as possible. I will maintain or even reduce my already low level of car use in the next months.	<input type="checkbox"/>

Q7 - Do you have at least one properly functioning bicycle? (Please tick one box!)

Yes	No
-----	----

Q8 - Do you have a driving license for a car? (Please tick one box!)

Yes	No
-----	----

Q9 - Do you have access to a car or van? (Please check one box!)

Yes	No
-----	----

Q10 - Do you have any annual/monthly/weekly ticket for public transport?

Yes	No
-----	----

Q11 - In the last seven days, how many days have you done 30 minutes or more of physical activity, which was enough to raise your heart rate and breathing rate? This may include sport, exercise, brisk walking, cycling or housework. The 30 minutes do not have to be done all at once, but one episode should last at least 10 minutes.

0 days	1 day	2 days	3 days
4 days	5 days	6 days	7 days

Q12.1 - Regular cycling or walking for everyday travel is a good thing to do for improving health.

I strongly disagree	<input type="checkbox"/>
I partly disagree	<input type="checkbox"/>
I partly agree	<input type="checkbox"/>
I strongly agree	<input type="checkbox"/>
I don't know / I don't have an opinion	<input type="checkbox"/>

Q12.2 - Physical activity helps prevent chronic diseases like cardiovascular diseases, diabetes, cancer, as well as strengthening mental health and bones.

I strongly disagree	<input type="checkbox"/>
I partly disagree	<input type="checkbox"/>
I partly agree	<input type="checkbox"/>
I strongly agree	<input type="checkbox"/>
I don't know / I don't have an opinion	<input type="checkbox"/>

Q12.3 - For children and their health it is important they are physically active for at least 60 minutes every day.

I strongly disagree	<input type="checkbox"/>
I partly disagree	<input type="checkbox"/>
I partly agree	<input type="checkbox"/>
I strongly agree	<input type="checkbox"/>
I don't know / I don't have an opinion	<input type="checkbox"/>

Q13 - Did you talk to your friends or colleagues about the SWITCH campaign?

Yes	No
-----	----

Q14 - Do you feel better informed about walking and cycling and how you benefit from active travel after having participated in the SWITCH campaign?

Yes	No
-----	----

Q15 - Are you more motivated to reduce car trips and travel by active modes such as walking and cycling since you have participated in our campaign?

Yes	No
-----	----

Q16 - Are other household members motivated to reduce car trips and travel by active modes like walking and cycling since you have participated in our campaign?

Yes, please outline who	No
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Q17 - Have there been any changes in your household since the last survey?

Yes, please outline who	No
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A short "thank you" to the respondents!

Q18 - We would like to get in touch in about five months to see if you are continuing any changes you made during the SWITCH campaign. If it would be okay to email you again, please type your email address here:

e-mail:

If you have any concerns about this questionnaire, the use of your data or if you would like to file a complaint about any aspect of this survey please contact ...

Endnotes

page	word/text passage	link / url
6	"transferability analysis"	bit.ly/1RSAk06
10	"the interview"	www.youtube.com/watch?v=_WUZVVIGay0
13	"recorded webinar"	www.youtube.com/watch?v=of3iyXqLmQM
13	"short interview"	bit.ly/1Rkr453
14	"target group"	bit.ly/SWITCH1J3eNUi
14	"health benefits"	bit.ly/SWITCH1Znttlj
14	"medical recommendations"	bit.ly/SWITCH1YyZFj8
14	"factsheets"	bit.ly/SWITCH1Qn9Xmj
14	"e.g. heart rate monitor, step counters, GPS watches"	bit.ly/SWITCH1LG9I5M
14	"Beat the Street"	www.youtube.com/watch?v=PcbG1hexfKE
15	"Wien zu Fuß"	bit.ly/SWITCH1oHnHOJ
15	"presentation"	www.youtube.com/watch?v=nxE9-SDy6X0
19	"brochure"	bit.ly/1QfVN50
20	"press material"	bit.ly/SWITCH1YyZ7tF
20	"factsheets"	bit.ly/SWITCH1Qn9Xmj
21	"tender document"	bit.ly/SWITCH1OIVL2a
21	"support staff"	bit.ly/SWITCH1R4912r
21	"material"	bit.ly/SWITCH1nbraJX
21	"facts"	bit.ly/SWITCH1Qn9Xmj
21	"map"	bit.ly/SWITCH1RfdoHT
21	"incentives"	bit.ly/SWITCH1nbmr15
22	"GPS watches, heart rate monitors, step counters, activity-logging websites and devices"	bit.ly/SWITCH1LG9I5M
24	"baseline data"	bit.ly/SWITCH1Mu0anO
24	"paper and pencil"	bit.ly/SWITCH1mpHqkk

page	word/text passage	link / url
24	"Toolbox"	bit.ly/SWITCH1nbraJX
25	"information flyer"	bit.ly/SWITCH1V2YDfh
25	"survey"	bit.ly/SWITCH1InyVQP
25	"sticker, button, balloon, safety vest, saddle cover, etc."	bit.ly/SWITCH1nbmr15
26	"press release"	bit.ly/SWITCH1YyZ7tF
28	"evaluation process"	bit.ly/SWITCH1JrXsiD
29	"action list"	bit.ly/SWITCH1JrXsiD
29	"guideline"	bit.ly/SWITCH1S8AoMY
29	"Toolbox"	bit.ly/SWITCH1O6OrB4
30	"paper letter"	bit.ly/SWITCH1mpHqkk
30	"Toolbox"	bit.ly/SWITCH1mpHqkk
31	"writing style"	bit.ly/SWITCH1V2YDfh
32	"baseline survey"	bit.ly/SWITCH1Mu0anO
34	"service sheet"	bit.ly/SWITCH1InyVQP
36	"information packages, PTP-Talks"	bit.ly/SWITCH1TINXUI
37	"good examples"	bit.ly/SWITCH22nPd2F
38	"Q1-Q5 and Q14"	bit.ly/SWITCH1Mu0anO
38	"Q1-Q5 and Q11"	bit.ly/SWITCH1U2D0ut
39	"1 st and a 2 nd "After-Engagement survey"	bit.ly/SWITCH1U2D0ut

SWITCH consortium

Five European Cities take the lead in SWITCH campaigns to support active modes of travel. They are supported by eight organisations with expertise in campaigning, health and economic aspects of walking and cycling. This enthusiastic team combines practical expertise, a clear and transferable methodology and tried and tested examples of locally effective campaigns.

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